

**PRADA MEETS VERSACE:
An Italian Luxury Consolidation**

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Abstract

This paper analyses the financial conditions of Gianni Versace S.r.l. and estimates its value in the context of a potential merger and acquisition (M&A) transaction by the Prada Group. The study pursues a dual objective: to determine Versace's economic value and to assess the potential synergies arising from the creation of an Italian luxury powerhouse capable of competing with French conglomerates.

The methodology initially involves reclassifying Versace's historical financial statements (covering the past 3–5 years) and conducting a financial analysis to evaluate profitability, capital structure, and liquidity. An examination of historical cash flows follows this to assess whether Versace can generate consistent cash flows.

Subsequently, a five-year projected financial statement is developed, accompanied by the corresponding financial analysis, from which the Free Cash Flow to the Firm (FCFF) is then derived.

The valuation of Versace will be carried out using three methods: the Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) model and the Dividend Discount Model (DDM) as the primary financial approaches, complemented by a multiples-based valuation to provide a more comprehensive perspective.

Finally, the paper offers an assessment of the transaction, exploring its potential impact on Prada as well as the risks associated with the M&A operation.

KEYWORDS

Company Valuation, M&A, DCF, DDM, Financial Analysis, Financial Statement Analysis, Comparable Company Analysis

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 LUXURY INDUSTRY CONTEXT

The luxury sector today represents one of the most complex and dynamic markets in the modern economy. Luxury can be understood as an articulated system that merges aesthetics, innovation, and industrial capabilities. In recent years, the industry has undergone a profound transformation driven by the continuous globalization of markets, the rise of Asian clientele (particularly Chinese), and the evolving needs of consumers. These changes have redefined competitive strategies and reshaped the business models adopted by companies operating in the sector.

A central feature of this transformation is the dominant role played by large multinational groups such as LVMH, Kering, and Richemont. These conglomerates have successfully assembled a portfolio of iconic brands. Through strategic acquisitions, they have built actual luxury holdings, leveraging economies of scale and centralised resource management. In contrast, independent maisons face increasingly complex challenges related to capital access, global visibility, and innovation capacity.

Within this context, mergers and acquisitions (M&A) have become essential tools for strengthening market position and securing the long-term sustainability of luxury brands. For smaller companies, M&A operations represent the most effective path to gain the resources and scale required to compete in a market dominated by global giants.

The acquisition of Gianni Versace S.r.l. by Prada could represent one of the most significant mergers between Italian brands, laying the foundation for the creation of a national luxury powerhouse capable of competing on the international stage, currently dominated by the major French groups.

1.2 GIANNI VERSACE S.R.L.

Versace is more than just a fashion brand; it is a symbol of Italian luxury that has successfully expanded worldwide thanks to its unmistakable, bold, and even provocative style. Founded in 1978 by Gianni Versace, the maison revolutionised the fashion industry through a powerful visual language characterised by vibrant colours, baroque prints, and references to classical art. The Medusa logo, symbolising charm and irresistible attraction, perfectly embodies the essence of the brand.

Over the years, Versace has established a strong and distinctive identity, seamlessly blending the elegance of Italian tailoring with a modern vision of the body and beauty. After the founder died in 1997, his sister, Donatella Versace, took over the creative direction,

guiding the company through a process of renewal while preserving its original spirit. In recent years, Versace has also undergone a managerial transformation, culminating in its acquisition by the American group Capri Holdings in 2018. This transaction provided the brand with a new vision, reinforcing its international presence and integrating it into a more structured and global framework.

Today, the brand operates worldwide through a network of directly owned boutiques and a diversified product portfolio ranging from apparel to accessories and home décor. Versace continues to be synonymous with luxury and creativity, representing a strategic opportunity for companies like Prada, which aspire to build a central Italian luxury hub capable of competing with French giants such as LVMH and Kering.

1.3 THE POTENTIAL BUYER: PRADA S.P.A.

Prada S.p.A. is one of the most prestigious Italian fashion houses and a global benchmark in the luxury sector. Founded in 1913 in Milan by Mario Prada as a boutique specialising in leather goods, the company underwent a profound transformation starting in the 1980s under the leadership of Miuccia Prada. The introduction of a minimalist, intellectual, and unconventional aesthetic vision turned the brand into a symbol of modernity, elegance, and innovation, clearly distinguishing it within the competitive landscape.

Today, the Prada Group manages a diversified portfolio of brands that, in addition to Prada, includes Miu Miu, Church's, Car Shoe, and Marchesi 1824, covering multiple luxury segments and ensuring a strong presence in global markets through an extensive retail network. The group's structure is vertically integrated, with direct control over production, distribution, and retail, ensuring both product quality and a seamless customer experience.

In recent years, Prada has strengthened its positioning strategy by accelerating its focus on sustainability, digitalisation, and innovation in distribution channels. Moreover, the group has maintained family governance while listing on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange in 2011, demonstrating its commitment to combining tradition with openness to global markets.

From a strategic perspective, Prada is in a favourable position to pursue expansion initiatives aimed at reinforcing its competitiveness. In particular, acquiring a brand like Versace would represent a unique opportunity to consolidate leadership in the Made in Italy luxury segment, broaden its customer base, and compete more effectively against major French conglomerates, such as LVMH and Kering.

1.4 THE HIPOTETICAL M&A TRANSACTION

The operation examined in this study considers the scenario in which Prada S.p.A. acquires the entirety of Gianni Versace S.r.l.'s capital, with the intention of creating an Italian luxury hub capable of competing—both in scale and positioning—with the major French conglomerates. In an increasingly consolidated sector, where groups such as LVMH and Kering have significantly expanded their brand portfolios through strategic acquisitions, the idea of a merger between two iconic Italian maisons carries considerable industrial and symbolic significance.

The importance of such a transaction rests on several key elements. First, the union of Prada and Versace would enable an expansion of both product offerings and customer base, leveraging their complementary stylistic identities and market positions. Prada represents the aesthetic and intellectual avant-garde of contemporary luxury, while Versace embodies exuberance and celebrates individuality. The integration of the two brands would provide broad coverage of the high-end segment, enabling them to target diverse audiences across various styles, age groups, and geographies.

Second, there are significant synergies on both the revenue and cost sides. Revenue synergies include reciprocal access to new markets and the ability to enhance each brand's customer base. Cost synergies would materialise through the creation of a shared supply chain and the unification of certain central functions. Furthermore, establishing a larger group could generate additional benefits, such as improved bargaining power with suppliers, greater attractiveness to talent, and more substantial negotiating leverage with the retail channel.

Ultimately, this transaction would contribute to a broader examination of Italy's role in the global luxury market. While many Italian brands have come under the control of foreign groups, a merger between Prada and Versace would represent a concrete attempt to establish national industrial leadership, thereby reinforcing the competitiveness of "Made in Italy" and safeguarding its strategic autonomy.

1.5 OBJECTIVES AND PAPER'S STRUCTURE

This paper aims to provide an in-depth analysis of the economic value of Gianni Versace S.r.l. and to assess the sustainability and strategic coherence of its potential acquisition by Prada S.p.A. In a context where the luxury sector is increasingly oriented toward the concentration of brands within large multinational groups, the central objective of this study is to understand whether the creation of an Italian luxury hub, through an M&A operation between two icons of Made in Italy, can represent a rational choice from financial,

industrial, and competitive perspectives.

The analysis is structured in several phases. First, Versace's economic and financial position is examined through the reclassification of historical financial statements and the construction of the cash flow statement, to evaluate the company's capital strength and ability to generate value as the target firm. Subsequently, a post-integration forecasted financial statement is developed, based on explicit assumptions regarding growth, investments, and operating synergies.

The second part of the study focuses on company valuation, carried out through the application of multiple methodologies: the Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) method, the Dividend Discount Model (DDM), and a market multiples analysis. This plurality of approaches enables the estimation of a credible value range, based on both standalone forecasts and market benchmarks.

Finally, the last section concentrates on the strategic analysis of the transaction, with particular emphasis on the degree of complementarity between the two brands, the potential for value creation through synergies, and the impact of the acquisition on Prada's key financial indicators.

Overall, the paper adopts an approach that combines financial analysis with strategic reflection, aiming to provide a comprehensive assessment of the proposed merger and acquisition (M&A) operation. The intent is not only to estimate the economic value of Versace, but also to determine whether integrating with Prada could generate sustainable long-term advantages. In an industry increasingly dominated by large international groups, this study seeks to contribute to the debate on the opportunity and feasibility of an Italian response, built on concrete industrial synergies and a long-term strategic vision.

2 RECLASSIFICATION AND HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF VERSACE

2.1 RECLASSIFICATION METHODOLOGY

To gain a comprehensive understanding of Gianni Versace S.r.l.'s economic and financial structure, it was necessary to reclassify the statutory financial statements according to consistent schemes. The Balance Sheet was reclassified based on the principle of managerial relevance, which enables the distinction between operating and non-operating assets and liabilities. The Income Statement was organized according to the value-added approach, providing a more effective reading of Versace's margin generation.

The structure of the reclassified Balance Sheet enables the calculation of key figures,

such as Net Invested Capital (NIC) and the related Net Financial Position (NFP), which determine the company's actual level of indebtedness.

The Income Statement was reclassified according to the value-added criterion, to progressively highlight, year by year, how the company's wealth was generated. It starts from operating revenues, from which net production costs, service costs, personnel expenses, and depreciation are deducted, leading to the Operating Result (EBIT).

The Cash Flow Statement was prepared using the indirect method, starting from the operating result and adjusting it for non-monetary items and changes in working capital. Its structure is divided into three sections: operating cash flows, investing cash flows, and financing cash flows. The primary objective is to assess the company's ability to generate liquidity through its core operations and to calculate the Free Cash Flow to the Firm (FCFF), a fundamental basis for business valuation through the DCF method. The elaboration was carried out in line with the managerial reclassification of both the Balance Sheet and the Income Statement, using the official financial statements of the most recent fiscal years.

The data used for the analysis were taken from the official financial statements of Gianni Versace S.r.l. covering the last five fiscal years.

2.2 RECLASSIFICATION OF THE BALANCE SHEET

For the specific purpose of evaluating Gianni Versace S.r.l., the Balance Sheet was reclassified according to the managerial relevance criterion, which is based on reorganizing financial statement items by their operating or financial function.

The following table presents the complete five-year reclassification of the Balance Sheet.

	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Extra					
fixed assets	312.531.785,84 €	296.905.087,51 €	280.350.093,06 €	262.881.492,04 €	244.474.083,73 €
stock	87.174.546,62 €	91.918.397,96 €	97.378.763,90 €	102.752.723,98 €	108.274.918,12 €
accounts receivable	204.883.296,64 €	216.032.605,00 €	228.865.912,62 €	241.496.143,58 €	254.474.763,88 €
liquidity	427.515.896,41 €	433.676.368,48 €	447.185.745,39 €	466.704.968,76 €	492.465.040,66 €
Total Assets	1.032.105.525,52 €	1.038.532.458,96 €	1.053.780.514,98 €	1.073.835.328,35 €	1.099.688.806,38 €
Equity	440.471.143,70 €	446.984.512,39 €	459.483.272,40 €	477.947.252,97 €	502.599.088,64 €
financial debts	241.763.099,41 €	248.348.645,80 €	229.489.115,80 €	209.796.803,92 €	189.115.560,30 €
long-term financial debts	213.401.348,59 €	219.214.330,32 €	202.567.252,48 €	185.185.088,20 €	166.930.005,89 €
short-term financial debts	28.361.750,82 €	29.134.315,48 €	26.921.863,32 €	24.611.715,73 €	22.185.554,41 €
accounts payables	349.871.282,41 €	343.199.300,76 €	364.808.126,77 €	386.091.271,46 €	407.974.157,44 €
Total Liabilities	1.032.105.525,52 €	1.038.532.458,96 €	1.053.780.514,98 €	1.073.835.328,35 €	1.099.688.806,38 €

Fig. 1: Historical balance sheet

This method enables the calculation of indicators such as Net Invested Capital (NIC)

and Net Operating Working Capital (NOWC). Subsequently, this enables the determination of the Net Financial Position (NFP) and Shareholders' Equity, essential components for understanding the company's financial structure and establishing a solid basis for valuation.

In particular:

- The Net Invested Capital (NIC) represents the amount the company has invested during the year under review and can be expressed as:

$$NIC = \text{Non-Operating Items} + \text{Fixed Assets} + \text{NOWC}$$

- The Net Operating Working Capital (NOWC) represents the amount the company has invested in its core operations, and is expressed as:

$$NOWC = \text{Stocks} + \text{Accounts Receivables} - \text{Accounts Payables}$$

- From another perspective, the Net Financial Position (NFP) is analyzed to identify the level of indebtedness sustained by the company in the year under review, net of cash and cash equivalents. This concept can be summarized as:

$$NFP = (\text{Long-term financial debts} - \text{Short-term financial debts}) - \text{Liquidity}$$

From a different viewpoint, the Net Financial Position (NFP) is analysed to determine the level of indebtedness sustained by the company during the year under review, net of cash and cash equivalents. This concept can be summarized as:

- The Fixed Capital Coverage Ratio measures the extent to which Fixed Capital (an alternative term for total fixed assets) is covered by Equity and medium/long-term debt. It is expressed as:

$$\text{Fixed Capital Coverage Ratio} = \frac{\text{Equity} + \text{Long-term financial debts}}{\text{Fixed Assets}}$$

- The Debt Ratio reflects financial leverage, i.e., the weight of debt capital compared to equity in financing business activities. It is used to assess the level of indebtedness that can enhance equity profitability while keeping financing risk under control. It is expressed as:

$$\text{Debt Ratio} = \frac{NFP}{\text{Equity}}$$

2.3 RECLASSIFICATION OF THE INCOME STATEMENT

In evaluating Gianni Versace S.r.l., the reclassification method based on value added was chosen, as it enables a more thorough analysis of the company's ability to generate wealth through its core business. Specifically, the adopted scheme sets operating revenues as the starting point, from which raw material costs and service costs are deducted to calculate the Gross Value Added, that is, the wealth produced internally by the company. From this figure, personnel expenses are deducted to obtain the Gross Operating Margin (GOM), also known internationally as EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortisation), a value that expresses the company's ability to create wealth through operating activities, net of depreciation and non-recurring items. EBITDA is also an indicator of operating efficiency, which will later be used for comparison with other operators in the fashion and luxury industry, and at the same time, represents the basis for preparing the Cash Flow Statement and the starting point in valuation using the multiples method.

In the next step, depreciation is subtracted from EBITDA to generate the value of the Operating Profit (OP), internationally known as EBIT (Earnings Before Interest and Taxes), an indicator that measures net operating efficiency, including non-monetary costs but excluding the effects of financial leverage and taxes. EBIT is also subsequently considered as a comparable index with other companies in the sector.

Finally, to arrive at Earnings Before Taxes, Net Financial Expenses and the balance of extraordinary items are deducted from EBIT. Then, taxes are deducted from Earnings Before Taxes to determine the Net Income.

In the table below, the reclassification of the Income Statement is observed over the last five years.

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Operating Revenues	623.802.000,00 €	437.544.000,00 €	711.114.000,00 €	773.171.000,00 €	686.455.000,00 €
Cost of goods sold	- 139.352.000,00 €	- 79.090.000,00 €	- 92.743.000,00 €	- 96.086.000,00 €	- 123.930.000,00 €
Cost of services	- 392.713.000,00 €	- 251.964.000,00 €	- 346.091.000,00 €	- 410.900.000,00 €	- 470.246.000,00 €
Added Value	91.737.000,00 €	106.490.000,00 €	272.280.000,00 €	266.185.000,00 €	92.279.000,00 €
Employee cost	- 143.401.000,00 €	- 88.916.000,00 €	- 92.019.000,00 €	- 106.453.000,00 €	- 106.035.000,00 €
EBITDA/MOL	- 51.664.000,00 €	17.574.000,00 €	180.261.000,00 €	159.732.000,00 €	13.756.000,00 €
Amortisation	- 42.491.000,00 €	- 33.253.000,00 €	- 24.476.000,00 €	- 26.488.000,00 €	- 58.136.000,00 €
EBIT/MON	- 94.155.000,00 €	15.679.000,00 €	155.785.000,00 €	133.244.000,00 €	71.892.000,00 €
Net Financial charges	- 11.206.000,00 €	- 2.053.000,00 €	- 3.707.000,00 €	- 10.242.000,00 €	- 28.478.000,00 €
Extraordinary components	- 14.656.000,00 €	110.526.000,00 €	2.063.000,00 €	3.112.000,00 €	1.029.000,00 €
Gross income	- 120.017.000,00 €	92.794.000,00 €	154.141.000,00 €	126.114.000,00 €	99.341.000,00 €
Operating taxes	1.644.000,00 €	54.521.000,00 €	- 38.361.000,00 €	- 37.040.000,00 €	26.757.000,00 €
Net Income	- 118.373.000,00 €	147.315.000,00 €	115.780.000,00 €	89.074.000,00 €	72.584.000,00 €

Fig. 2: Historical income statement

2.4 FINANCIAL ANALYSIS

The analysis will focus on evaluating Gianni Versace S.r.l., dividing the study into four main areas: Profitability analysis, capital structure analysis, liquidity analysis, and financial liquidity analysis. The assessments presented in the following paragraphs are based on the summary framework shown below.

ASSET ANALYSIS					
	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
NIC	247.878.000,00 €	439.179.000,00 €	231.138.000,00 €	327.005.000,00 €	296.814.000,00 €
NOIC	247.878.000,00 €	439.179.000,00 €	231.138.000,00 €	327.005.000,00 €	296.814.000,00 €
NFP	62.836.000,00 €	102.052.000,00 €	- 202.164.000,00 €	- 196.800.000,00 €	- 148.357.000,00 €
NOWC	- 85.287.000,00 €	146.795.000,00 €	- 50.976.000,00 €	- 39.031.000,00 €	- 30.538.000,00 €
day sales outstanding	94	308	70	76	102
day payable outstanding	179	228	130	139	162
day inventory outstanding	36	40	34	45	44
CASH CONVERSION CYCLE	- 49	121	- 26	- 18	- 16
Fixed capital covered ratio	0,70	1,32	1,69	3,01	3,11
Debt ratio	0,34	0,30	-0,47	-0,38	-0,33
PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS					
	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
ISCR	7,58	-2,08	21,14	18,70	-10,52
ROI	-37,98%	-3,57%	67,40%	40,75%	-24,22%
ROI (1-tc)	-28,87%	-2,71%	51,22%	30,97%	-18,41%
ROS	-15,09%	-3,58%	21,91%	17,23%	-10,47%
ROE	-63,97%	43,70%	26,72%	17,01%	-16,30%
ROD	17,83%	2,01%	-1,83%	-5,20%	-19,20%
Turnover	2,52	1,00	3,08	2,36	2,31
Operating Revenue	623.802.000,00 €	437.544.000,00 €	711.114.000,00 €	773.171.000,00 €	686.455.000,00 €
NET INCOME	- 118.373.000,00 €	147.315.000,00 €	115.780.000,00 €	89.074.000,00 €	- 72.584.000,00 €
LIQUIDITY ANALYSIS					
	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
CURRENT RATIO	0,72	1,27	1,72	3,31	3,09
QUICK RATIO	0,55	1,13	1,47	3,00	2,84
CASH RATIO	0,10	0,03	0,96	2,49	2,25
FINANCIAL ANALYSIS					
	2021	2022	2023	2024	
DSCR	144	-11	24	1	
INCREMENTAL NET WORTH					
Δ NOWC	232.082.000,00 €	- 197.771.000,00 €	11.945.000,00 €	8.493.000,00 €	
SHORT NFP	14.160.000,00 €	53.623.000,00 €	- 245.257.000,00 €	- 773.413.000,00 €	

Fig. 3: Historical summary framework

2.4.1 PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS

Through profitability analysis, it is possible to determine how much the company can generate in profits based on sales, Net Invested Capital, and Equity. In other words, this analysis helps us to understand whether the company is capable of remunerating capital providers, relying on various profitability ratios:

- Return on Equity (ROE), which measures the return on Equity invested by share-

holders. It is calculated as follows:

$$ROE = \frac{NetIncome}{Equity}$$

- Return on Investment (ROI), which identifies the company's ability to generate profits from its core activity in relation to the Invested Capital. It is calculated as follows:

$$ROI = \frac{EBIT}{NIC + NoN - Operating\ Items}$$

- Return on Debt (ROD), which determines the cost of debt, and is expressed as:

$$ROD = \frac{Net\ Financial\ Charges}{NFP}$$

In particular, ROI and ROD are compared to evaluate the economic equilibrium of the company, which occurs only if the following relation holds:

$$ROI > ROD$$

- Return on Sales (ROS), which helps estimate the portion of sales revenues that can be defined as actual profit for the company. It is expressed as:

$$ROS = \frac{EBIT}{Operating\ Revenues}$$

- EBITDA Margin, which indicates the percentage of Operating Revenues that the company retains before incurring non-operating costs. It is calculated as:

$$EBITDA\ Margin = \frac{EBITDA}{Operating\ Revenues}$$

In the specific case, Versace S.r.l. did not exhibit stable and solid profitability during the analysed period (2020–2024), due to both exogenous and endogenous factors, as can be observed from the charts reported below.

Fig. 4: Profitability Analysis

Fig. 5: Net Income

In general, this can be observed by analysing the trend of ROE, which recorded a sharp increase between 2020 and 2021, rising from -63.97% to $+26.72\%$, and then showing a downward trend until reaching a negative value of -16.30% in 2024. This performance can be explained by analysing the components of the same indicator, specifically Net Income. As shown in the chart 5, the Net Income recovered in 2021, remained stable until 2023, and then suffered a drastic decline in 2024, ultimately returning to a loss. The trend can be explained by the movement of operating revenues and various operating costs: in 2020 and 2021, they fell due to the COVID-19 crisis, before recovering in 2022 and 2023.

In 2024, however, revenues decreased while costs (especially service costs) increased, a situation justified by the outbreak of the war in Ukraine and in Palestine.

To fully understand the company's trend, it is essential to analyse ROI and ROD together, as this enables the evaluation of both the efficiency of Versace's operating management and the economic convenience of debt. The chart 4 highlights that between 2020 and 2024 the indices show strong instability and significant fluctuations, reflecting the company's exposure to cyclical and extraordinary factors. In 2020, ROI displayed a strongly negative value, explained by a negative EBIT and a high level of Net Operating Invested Capital (NOIC = NIC + Extra). This demonstrates that the company was committing a high level of capital without achieving an equal economic return; in other words, the company was destroying value. In the same year, ROD was positive (17.83%), indicating a high cost of debt, and compared to ROI, it highlights an economic imbalance, as debt costs were higher than the ROI.

In 2021 the situation improved, but the company still presented an economic imbalance. Specifically, the ROI increased, although it remained negative, and the ROD decreased, although it remained higher than the ROI. These changes were supported by an increase in EBIT (resulting from a reduction in costs) and a strong growth in NOIC (caused by a significant increase in receivables, a decrease in trade payables, and a possible clearance of inventories that led to a decline in operating revenues).

By contrast, considering the two years 2022–2023, it can be observed that the company was in economic equilibrium, thanks to a substantial increase in ROI and a downward trend in ROD, which fell into negative values. More precisely, the growth in ROI was due to a significant rise in EBIT (driven by strong growth in operating revenues) and to a sharp reduction in NOIC (caused by a fall in trade receivables).

Unfortunately, in 2024 the company returned to economic disequilibrium, since both debt capital and equity capital failed to generate value. This situation is due to a continued decline in ROD, although less severe than the decline in ROI. The significant deterioration in ROI reflects an inverse relationship between revenues and operating costs, resulting in a substantial decline in profitability.

This overall trend in profitability and economic–financial balance is further confirmed by the evaluation of turnover. During the period under review, the strong volatility of turnover reflects the instability already shown by the indicators: in the years when invested capital was used efficiently, turnover reached high levels, sustaining operating profitability; in the years when invested capital increased strongly without being accompanied by a proportional rise in revenues, turnover contracted, which then led to a fall in ROI and ROE.

Another ratio that helps to analyse the company's ability to transform sales into net profit

is ROS. It is worth noting that in 2020, 2021, and 2024, the ROS was negative, whereas it had positive values only during the two years from 2022 to 2023. From this, it can be concluded that the company demonstrates profitability only when influenced by external economic recoveries; however, it also suffers from a structural weakness in generating profits. This observation is further confirmed by the performance of the EBITDA Margin, which showed a very irregular trend between 2020 and 2024. During periods of growth, the operating leverage enabled the company to achieve margin levels comparable to those of its main international competitors. Conversely, during periods of sales contraction, the margin deteriorated rapidly, reaching harmful levels due to the company's inability to reduce operating costs proportionally.

2.4.2 ASSET ANALYSIS

This analysis is based on various balance sheet ratios:

- Cash Conversion Cycle: represents the period between the collection of receivables and the repayment of debt. It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Cash Conversion Cycle} = \text{Days Sales Outstanding} + \text{Days Inventory Outstanding} - \text{Days Payable}$$

- Fixed Capital Coverage Ratio: a measure of capital structure soundness that evaluates whether fixed capital investments are covered by equity and medium/long-term debt. It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Fixed Capital Coverage Ratio} = \frac{\text{Equity} + \text{Long term financial debts}}{\text{Fixed Assets}}$$

- Debt Ratio: a financial structure indicator that shows the extent to which the company relies on debt capital compared to Equity in financing its operations. It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Debt Ratio} = \frac{\text{NFP}}{\text{Equity}}$$

With reference to Versace S.r.l., one of the ratios that helps explain the capital structure is the Cash Conversion Cycle and its components (days receivables, days inventory, and days payables). Starting from receivable days, they show high volatility, with very high peaks during periods of low operating revenues, thus requiring greater working capital needs. Likewise, the average payment period to suppliers varies significantly, ranging from 130 days to over 220 days, suggesting the company's ability to obtain extended payment terms in times of crisis. At the same time, inventory turnover remains stable, justified by efficient warehouse management. Overall, the Cash Conversion Cycle showed negative

values in several fiscal years, indicating that the company collects cash before paying its suppliers and therefore does not require external financing to meet its commitments. This assumption is confirmed by the analysis of the Fixed Capital Coverage Ratio, which shows values greater than one in all fiscal years since 2021, highlighting strong balance sheet equilibrium. Unfortunately, in 2020, a disequilibrium was observed, explained by the need to rely on short-term debt to finance Fixed Capital. To improve this critical situation, the company pursued a strategy of increasing Equity.

To achieve capital structure equilibrium, it is essential to maintain an adequate financial leverage, which can be inferred from the trend of the Debt Ratio. Indeed, in 2020–2021, the values observed were not excessively high, underlining a balanced capital structure, with moderate use of debt compared to Equity. A substantial improvement can be observed, especially from 2022, when the ratio began to show negative values, indicating a positive Net Financial Position, as cash holdings exceeded financial debt.

2.4.3 LIQUIDITY ANALYSIS

Liquidity analysis is a fundamental evaluation tool used to determine whether a company can meet its short-term obligations and assess the adequacy of its capital structure in supporting the business's sustainability. For this purpose, three leading indicators have been studied: the Current Ratio (CR), the Quick Ratio (QR) and the Cash Ratio (CaR), each characterised by an increasingly higher level of precision in assessing corporate solvency. These three ratios, observed together, provide the opportunity to represent the historical evolution of the ability to cover current liabilities, while also allowing for the study of liquidity variation.

The first indicator is the Current Ratio, which assesses whether the company can meet its current liabilities by relying on short-term resources, regardless of its level of immediate liquidity. Current assets are composed of trade receivables, cash and inventories. Current liabilities, on the other hand, consist of financial debts and trade payables. It is calculated through the following formula:

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

A value higher than 1 indicates a condition of equilibrium, since current assets are sufficient to cover short-term obligations.

Subsequently, the Quick Ratio is considered, which represents a stricter version of the Current Ratio, because inventories are excluded from the numerator, focusing only on current assets that can be liquidated quickly (receivables and cash). This ratio aims to reduce the distortions that inventories may cause. The formula representing the Quick

Ratio is:

$$QR = \frac{\text{Accounts Receivable} + \text{Liquidity}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Finally, the Cash Ratio is the most precise indicator, which evaluates the company's ability to cover current liabilities by relying solely on cash or cash equivalents. It provides a rigorous assessment of a company's short-term financial soundness, determining whether it can meet its current debts immediately without resorting to either receivables or inventories. Analytically, it is calculated as follows:

$$CaR = \frac{\text{Liquidity}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

A value above 1 implies that the company has sufficient cash resources to extinguish its current liabilities without depending on future collections or inventory.

In 2020, all the indicators revealed a situation of disequilibrium. The Current Ratio stood at 0.72, the Quick Ratio at 0.55 and the Cash Ratio at 0.1. This critical condition can be explained by the current liabilities of €360.6 million (comprising €309.4 million in trade payables and €51.1 million in short-term financial debt) compared with current assets of €261.1 million. Cash and cash equivalents totalled only €36.9 million, covering approximately 10% of current obligations. Accounts receivable represented the largest share of current assets, but did not guarantee immediate repayment capacity. Inventories, amounting to €62 million, were challenging to liquidate in the short term. Overall, the company was in a position of extreme dependence on supplier payment extensions and on the possibility of taking out short-term debt.

The year 2021 marked the first sign of improvement, with CR rising to 1.27 and QR to 1.13. However, CaR fell to 0.03, highlighting a sharp deterioration in immediate liquidity. The composition of current assets can explain this inconsistency, since receivables increased to €374.7 million, fully supporting the coverage of current liabilities, which amounted to €339.8 million. The cash balance decreased to a historic low of €9.7 million. The immediate liquidity ratio, although above the threshold that guarantees balance, was based on commercial items rather than actual cash, indicating a liquidity structure that remains fragile and overly dependent on expected collections.

In 2022, the balance improved significantly. CR stood at 1.72, QR at 1.47 and CaR at 0.95. This improvement was primarily due to the increase in cash and equivalents, which reached €261 million, covering almost the entire current liabilities of €271.6 million on its own. Inventories amounted to €66.7 million, while receivables decreased to €138.2 million. At the same time, short-term financial debt dropped to €15.8 million, reducing liquidity pressure. Indicators improved thanks to the increasing weight of cash compared with less liquid items.

The year 2023 marked the peak of improvement, with CR reaching 3.31, QR at 3.00, and CaR at 2.49. Cash rose sharply to €793.7 million, while current liabilities totalled €318.2 million. Cash alone covered 2.5 times current liabilities, generating a substantial margin of coverage. However, this strengthening was not only due to an improvement in operating management but was intrinsically linked to the sharp increase in long-term debt, which rose to €576.6 million. Part of the cash surplus was the result of new long-term financing resources allocated to the company's treasury, rather than an increase in operating cash flows.

Finally, in 2024, indicators remained relatively stable, albeit with a slight reduction. CR fell to 3.09, QR to 2.84, and CaR to 2.25. Cash decreased to €744.6 million, while receivables increased to €195 million, accompanied by a simultaneous rise in current liabilities, which rose to €331.1 million. The quality of liquidity remained excellent, as cash alone still covered more than twice the current liabilities; however, the growth of working capital (receivables and payables) indicated a utilisation of resources by operating management. Overall, Versace's liquidity trend showed a clear evolution, moving from a condition of severe disequilibrium in 2020—characterised by indicators below the minimum balance threshold and heavy dependence on suppliers—towards a phase of balance in the 2022–2024 period, supported by a significant increase in cash and a contraction in current liabilities. The liquidity structure improved progressively. While in 2021, the balance was based almost exclusively on receivables, from 2022 onwards, cash became the primary source of coverage. Nevertheless, the high cash surplus observed in 2023 and 2024 did not derive solely from operating activity; however, it was mainly explained by the sharp increase in long-term financial debt, which inflated treasury cash. The immediate effect was a very safe short-term balance, but in a medium- to long-term perspective, this will translate into greater debt exposure.

The issue of over-liquidity, therefore, arises: an excess of cash, which, if not properly allocated, risks becoming a management inefficiency and an opportunity cost. From one perspective, over liquidity represents a strength, as it can be seen as a reserve that enhances bargaining power and attractiveness in the context of M&A. At the same time, this situation can turn into a challenge for Versace, which will need not only to preserve and further strengthen its current solidity, but above all to use the excess cash effectively, either through possible investments or by reducing debt, thus reinforcing the financial position and ensuring a lasting balance between Equity and debt capital that is maintaining a balanced financial structure.

2.4.4 FINANCIAL ANALYSIS

Financial analysis represents a key element in assessing the sustainability of debt, and, in a broader sense, the degree of solvency of the company.

To support progressive growth, Versace gradually employed debt capital, a choice that, on the one hand, allowed an increase in resources and optimisation of equity returns, but on the other hand, triggered a structural rigidity linked to the payment of interest and the repayment of principal.

It therefore becomes essential to examine whether Versace, with operating cash flows alone, has been able to cover the cost of debt without compromising the solidity of its financial structure.

For this purpose, two fundamental indicators have been used. The first is the Debt Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR). This indicator measures the company's ability to service debt repayment relying solely on cash flows.

It is obtained by comparing Free Cash Flow from Operations (FCFO) with the sum of financial charges and debt repayment instalments.

In the case of Versace, the formula has been adapted by considering the structure of a single repayment at maturity (Bullet Bond) of the medium/long-term financial debt:

$$DSCR = \frac{FCFO}{NFC + Repayment}$$

In addition to the DSCR, in order to provide a more accurate assessment of Versace's financial position, it was necessary to analyse the incremental Equity, expressed by the following relation:

$$Incremental\ Equity = \Delta NOWC \geq NFP_{short-term}$$

The variation of the Net Operating Working Capital (NOWC) must be compared with the evolution of the short-term Net Financial Position (NFP).

A value of the variation in NOWC greater than the NFP indicates that the company is in a position to take on new debt during the financial year, since financial requirements are covered by working capital.

From the analysis, it emerges that Versace's DSCR shows significant variations during the period 2020–2024, due to the combined effect of operating margin volatility and the gradual increase in financial leverage. In 2020, a negative EBIT (€–94.1 million) and financial charges of €11.2 million weakened the company's ability to service debt, reflecting the operational difficulties caused by the health emergency. In 2021, the gradual recovery of demand following the pandemic significantly contributed to Versace's improvement

in economic and financial balance. Moreover, less onerous refinancing policies allowed the company to reduce financial charges to €2 million. The combination of these two phenomena led to an initial improvement in the DSCR. Thanks to the strengthening of the accessories segment, the renewal of the retail network, and the development of the digital channel, 2022 marked a year of excellent financial solidity, with revenues rising to €711.1 million and EBIT reaching €155.7 million, resulting in higher margins. The increase in revenues and EBIT was directly reflected in Net Income, which rose to €115.8 million, the highest value in the five years. The combined effect of these dynamics supported a strengthening of the DSCR, ensuring greater debt coverage capacity. Starting from 2023, debt increased significantly (total financial debt of €596.9 million, of which €576.6 million is long-term), leading to higher financial charges of €10.2 million together with a simultaneous decline in profitability. In 2024, the decline in consumption in Europe and Asia, combined with increased competition in the luxury sector, led to a reduction in Versace's market share, resulting in revenues falling to €686.5 million. EBIT decreased to €71.9 million, and Net Income decreased to €72.6 million, indicating a contraction of operating margins and a limited ability to cover fixed costs. Despite holding very high cash reserves (€744.5 million), the accumulated debt in recent years was insufficient to offset the decline in operating profitability. The fluctuations in DSCR over the five years are attributable to the combined effects of slowing revenue growth, declining margins, and increasing debt exposure.

At the same time, the analysis of incremental Equity highlights a two-phase trend, the result of specific operational and financial dynamics. In the years 2020–2021–2022, the variation of NOWC was greater than the short-term NFP, indicating that Versace was in incremental balance, with the ability to take on additional debt. This trend was supported by the recovery in revenues after the pandemic crisis, the increase in sales, and a more efficient management of working capital, thanks to improvements in the handling of receivables and inventories. These elements enabled the company to generate sufficient resources to finance growth without relying on short-term debt. Unfortunately, in 2023–2024 the situation reversed. With the increase in medium- to long-term debt contracted to support development plans and strategic investments, NFP exceeded its working capital. Moreover, a slowdown in revenue growth reduced the ability to generate operating cash flows. In addition, the increase in operating costs and the higher structural rigidity of management reduced the company's flexibility in making decisions or reacting to external shocks. These combined factors created a condition of incremental balance sheet disequilibrium, where the weight of debt reduced self-financing capacity and the ability to cover financial requirements through internal resources.

Ultimately, these fluctuations are attributable to specific causes such as the 2020 pandemic

crisis, the recovery of 2021–2022, and the debt expansion in 2023, which increased costs and financial charges. Versace managed to maintain its ability to meet financial commitments, but with growing debt exposure, making capital structure management crucial, especially in view of the acquisition and the consequent need to redefine the balance between Equity and debt capital.

2.4.5 INTEREST COVERAGE RATIO

Alongside the DSCR and incremental Equity, the Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR) constitutes another important indicator for assessing the sustainability of a firm's financial structure, as it measures the ability of operating profit (EBIT) to cover financial charges. Analytically, it is calculated as follows:

$$ICR = \frac{EBIT}{Financial\ Charges}$$

Where EBIT (Earnings Before Interest and Taxes) indicates operating profit before financial charges and taxes, while financial charges represent the cost of debt.

If the ratio assumes values below 1, then the company is unable to cover its interest through operating activities alone. Values above 2–3 are considered optimal, as they ensure a good safety margin. Very high ratios could indicate a limited use of financial leverage.

In the case of Gianni Versace S.r.l., the historical trend exhibits high volatility, alternating years of solid performance with periods of crisis.

In 2020, the ICR was 7.58, a reassuring level that highlights a strong coverage capacity: EBIT was sufficient to guarantee the full coverage of financial charges. Despite a complex context and declining revenues, the company managed to maintain a stable position, thanks to a controlled debt cost.

The situation worsened in 2021, when the ratio fell to –2.08. The negative value resulted from a loss-making EBIT, which meant the company was unable to cover its debt costs, making them unsustainable. This weakness can be attributed to a decline in revenues and the resulting reduction in margins. This outcome highlights how, in an adverse scenario, the company becomes more exposed to financial tensions and risks, deteriorating its capital structure.

The year 2022 marked a clear turning point. The ICR reached 21.14, supported by very high EBIT, the result of volume recovery and rising operating margins. Financial charges, which remained relatively contained, only amplified the effect, pushing the ratio to a level of absolute solidity.

However, this value must be interpreted with caution, as it reflects a very favourable context for the company and does not necessarily represent a sustainable balance in the long

term.

The positive trend continued in 2023, when the ratio stabilised at 18.7, still at levels of absolute stability. EBIT remained more than sufficient to cover all financial charges.

This year marked a phase of strengthening, during which the combination of high operating flows and low debt costs enabled the company to maintain a sound financial profile.

Finally, in 2024, the ICR turned negative again (−10.52), reflecting a loss-making EBIT alongside rising financial charges. The contraction in revenues, combined with the increase in the cost of debt, generated a disequilibrium in the financial structure.

Overall, the evolution of ICR between 2020 and 2024 depicts a picture of strong instability. Versace alternated phases of financial solidity (2020, 2022 and 2023) with phases of severe disequilibrium (2021 and 2024), demonstrating a financial structure susceptible to cyclical fluctuations in the luxury sector and to credit market conditions.

This volatility reflects two critical factors: on the one hand, exposure to demand variability; on the other hand, dependence on debt cost conditions.

3 CASH FLOW ANALYSIS

	2021	2022	2023	2024
EBITDA	17.574.000,00 €	180.261.000,00 €	159.732.000,00 €	- 13.756.000,00 €
ΔCCNO	- 232.082.000,00 €	197.771.000,00 €	- 11.945.000,00 €	- 8.493.000,00 €
Operating taxes	54.521.000,00 €	- 38.361.000,00 €	- 37.040.000,00 €	26.757.000,00 €
NET CASH FLOW	- 159.987.000,00 €	339.671.000,00 €	110.747.000,00 €	4.508.000,00 €
CAPEX	7.528.000,00 €	- 14.206.000,00 €	- 110.410.000,00 €	- 19.452.000,00 €
Extraordinary Incomes/ Expenses	110.526.000,00 €	2.063.000,00 €	3.112.000,00 €	1.029.000,00 €
-VARIAZIONE EXTRA	- €	- €	- €	- €
+APP/RIDUZ CAPITALE PR	4.770.000,00 €	- 19.605.000,00 €	1.429.000,00 €	- 6.050.000,00 €
Net financial charges	- 2.053.000,00 €	- 3.707.000,00 €	- 10.242.000,00 €	- 28.478.000,00 €
+VARIAZIONE PFN M-L	- 247.000,00 €	- 5.336.000,00 €	533.520.000,00 €	- 2.999.000,00 €
+VARIAZIONE PFN BREVE	39.463.000,00 €	- 298.880.000,00 €	- 528.156.000,00 €	51.442.000,00 €

Fig. 6: Historical Statement of Cash Flows

Following the analysis of debt sustainability through the evaluation of the DSCR and incremental Equity, it is necessary to examine the evolution of cash flows, as they represent the expression of Versace's ability to generate financial resources and manage its level of indebtedness. The assessment of operating flows allows the extension and completion of the analysis of Versace's historical financial sustainability.

In this context, the operating cash flow (net operating cash flow) plays a crucial role, as it represents the company's ability to generate sufficient resources to finance investments without resorting to new debt. In 2021, strongly negative values were recorded (€−159.9 million), reflecting the direct impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, which caused a sharp fall

in revenues with a consequent negative EBIT (€-94.1 million), while costs (personnel and services) maintained a significant weight on revenues. In 2022, a reversal of trend can be observed, with cash flows rising to €339.7 million, supported by growing demand in international markets, the expansion of e-commerce, and more efficient working capital management. In 2023, although Versace reached peak revenues (€773 million), operating flows decreased to €110.7 million due to higher service and personnel costs, which compressed operating margins. In 2024, a further decline in cash flows can be observed, falling to €4.5 million. This reduction can be attributed to a renewed slowdown in global demand for luxury goods caused by the outbreak of the wars in the Middle East and between Russia and Ukraine, a greater incidence of costs on revenues, and rising competition in the sector, which limited Versace's ability to convert increased volumes into cash flows.

Building on this analysis, investment cash flows are considered to evaluate the extent to which new fixed capital investments impacted available liquidity. This type of cash flow reflects the CAPEX policies undertaken by the company during the year. In the biennium 2021–2022, investments remained limited (€7.5 million and €14.2 million), showing that in a context influenced by the pandemic, the company preferred a cautious approach. The year 2023 marked a significant shift, with CAPEX rising to a historical peak of €110.4 million, highlighting a likely plan to strengthen the retail network, renovate various stores, and expand the digital channel. This growth reflects the desire to leverage the recovery of the global luxury market by diversifying profit drivers with a focus on accessories. Finally, in 2024, CAPEX levels remained higher than during the COVID period, supporting investments in digital and new store openings.

The trend of financing cash flows is closely linked to investment policies, since debt financing represented the primary source for the expansion plan adopted by Versace. Financing flows were the main factor influencing liquidity variation. In 2021, following the post-pandemic recovery, the company resorted to short-term debt (€39.5 million) to support working capital, which was strongly absorbed by the renewed growth in sales. At the same time, equity contributions (€4.8 million) and limited financial charges (€2.1 million) helped maintain financial stability during a transition phase. In 2022, financial strength was reinforced through medium- to long-term debt (€5.3 million) and additional short-term borrowing. This choice enabled the company to accumulate liquidity, creating a cash reserve that was useful for supporting growth and maintaining financial balance in an uncertain context. In 2023, the strategy underwent a radical shift. Versace substantially increased medium- to long-term debt (€533.5 million) with a dual objective: on the one hand, extending maturities to reduce short-term liquidity risk, and on the other hand, increasing cash reserves. The implication was higher financial charges, which rose to €10.2 million due to greater indebtedness. In 2024, debt variations eased, but the debt

contracted in previous years had an impact, with financial charges rising sharply to €28.5 million. The strategy of maintaining high liquidity guaranteed stability, but involved a significant debt cost.

The analysis of cash flows (operating, investing, and financing) shows how Versace consolidated its financial strength through policies aimed at preserving liquidity and supporting growth. In 2021, despite negative cash flows resulting from working capital absorption, the company maintained a financial balance, thanks to its short-term debt, thereby avoiding short-term disequilibrium. The year 2022 marked the peak of cash flow generation, driven by improved operating margins and the release of working capital, which enhanced liquidity. Versace's strategy in 2023 underwent a significant shift with heavy refinancing: the company replaced its short-term debt with medium- to long-term debt. This choice improved liquidity management, although it led to higher debt costs. In 2024, on the one hand, net debt variations eased, but on the other, the cost of external capital showed its effects, producing disequilibrium in current management.

In summary, the cash flow analysis highlights how Versace was able to combine growth with a strong cash position, but also shows that this development created increasing dependence on debt. The aim is not only to maintain liquidity but also to control the cost of external capital during the acquisition phase, thereby restoring balance between self-financing, investments, and debt capital.

4 FIVE-YEAR FORECAST FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

4.1 ASSUMPTIONS UNDERLYING THE FORECASTS

The economic and financial projections estimated for Gianni Versace S.r.l. over the period 2025–2029 are based on a set of assumptions developed around four fundamental pillars: the macroeconomic scenario, industry dynamics in the luxury sector, the company-specific characteristics defining Versace's business model, and the potential synergies arising from the acquisition by Prada S.p.A. This methodological framework makes it possible to design a forward-looking financial plan that does not merely replicate historical performance, but instead coherently integrates exogenous variables (GDP growth, inflation, interest rates), endogenous factors, and strategic impacts related to the process of industrial and financial integration. In this way, the model aims to provide a reliable and well-founded representation of the expected growth trajectory, serving as the basis for the subsequent economic and financial valuation of the company.

The macroeconomic scenario used as a benchmark is based on GDP growth forecasts for the main markets in which Versace operates, with a specific focus on the Americas, EMEA,

and Asia, weighted according to the revenue distribution by geographical area. This methodology enables the incorporation of the diverse growth dynamics of the reference regions into the forecast model, avoiding the adoption of a single, constant growth rate that would be poorly representative of the company's actual geographic exposure.

Based on these assumptions, it was possible to estimate a weighted annual revenue growth rate consistent with both macroeconomic dynamics and the geographic composition of Versace's sales. In this way, the revenue forecast reflects not only the sectoral outlook but also the company's ability to adapt to different economic contexts, thereby ensuring greater alignment with its operational reality.

As regards the cost structure, the estimation of the main operating items was carried out by combining two approaches: on the one hand, the analysis of the historical average percentage incidence observed over the period 2020–2024; on the other, the application of linear regression to model the statistical relationships between revenues and selected cost components. This hybrid approach enables the integration of the stability of historical evidence with the predictive capacity of econometric tools, thereby yielding more robust projections that are consistent with revenue evolution. Specifically:

The Cost of Goods Sold (COGS) and personnel costs were estimated based on their historical average percentage of operating revenues. Specifically, for each year in the period 2020–2024, the ratio between the individual cost item and operating revenues was calculated. Subsequently, the average was calculated to obtain a representative value of the company's typical operating structure. This value was then used as the forecast incidence percentage, which was applied to projected revenues to estimate future costs. In this manner, projected COGS were calculated by multiplying the average incidence by the expected revenues for each year in the 2025–2029 period. The same approach was adopted for personnel costs, ensuring methodological consistency between the two main operating expense categories. The adoption of this method enables the preservation of operating margin stability. It maintains a close correlation between revenue dynamics and direct cost trends, assuming no significant changes in production processes or workforce composition.

Service costs were estimated using the statistical tool of linear regression, applying the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. This econometric technique enables the estimation of the relationship between two variables by identifying the line that minimises the sum of squared deviations between the observed and predicted values in the model. In this case, the independent variable considered was operating revenues, while the dependent variable was represented by service costs recorded over the historical period from 2020 to 2024. The application of the OLS method yielded a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.7, indicating a significant correlation between the dynamics of revenues and those of

service costs. Once the regression equation was estimated, the coefficients of the linear function (intercept a and slope b) were calculated. Forecasted service costs were then determined by applying the estimated equation, i.e., by multiplying the slope coefficient b by the projected operating revenues and adding the intercept a . This approach enables the derivation of a projection that does not merely replicate a historical average value but instead integrates the incremental dynamics of costs as revenues fluctuate, yielding a more consistent and realistic estimate of the company's operational performance.

Forecasted net financial charges were estimated as the difference between interest expenses and financial income.

Interest expenses were determined by applying a cost of debt rate (R_d) to the annual average of gross financial debt, calculated as the arithmetic mean between end-of-year and beginning-of-year values. The R_d rate was estimated using an additive approach, obtained by summing the risk-free rate (R_f) and a spread reflecting the risk profile of a non-listed company operating in the luxury sector. This spread accounts for both sector risk linked to the cyclical nature and sensitivity of the fashion industry to macroeconomic trends, as well as firm-specific risk, given Versace's status as a medium-sized company with limited financial diversification. Financial income, on the other hand, was estimated by applying a 0.5% return rate to the average cash holdings available in each forecast year. This assumption reflects a prudent yield, consistent with typical treasury management in the absence of complex financial investment policies. The adoption of this methodology enables the representation of the net cost of the financial structure across the entire 2025–2029 forecast horizon, ensuring that the dynamics of financial charges accurately reflect both the evolution of the debt position and the company's ability to generate cash and ancillary returns. Regarding working capital, the following assumptions were made.

1. The forecast of operating revenues was carried out using the Revenue/GDP elasticity model, which makes it possible to estimate the sensitivity of sales to the macroeconomic performance of the reference markets. The model was applied to historical and forecasted GDP growth rates of the three main geographic areas in which Versace operates: America, EMEA, and Asia. The expected percentage change in revenues was calculated by combining three key elements:

- the GDP growth rates (historical and forecasted) for each geographic area;
- the percentage distribution of revenues by area (America 33%, EMEA 43%, Asia 24%), representing the weight of each market on total sales;
- the historical elasticity of revenues to GDP, calculated as the ratio between the percentage change in revenues and the percentage change in GDP in the

respective markets.

In this way, revenue growth reflects both the macroeconomic dynamics of the markets and Versace's ability to amplify or mitigate such trends through its structure and competitive positioning. The adoption of the Revenue/GDP elasticity model ensures consistent and realistic revenue projections.

2. Accounts receivables and inventories were estimated by applying to forecasted operating revenues the respective historical incidences, measured in terms of collection days and inventory turnover. Specifically, trade receivables were estimated under the assumption that the company maintains average collection periods consistent with the 2020–2024 historical period, expressed as the ratio between receivables and daily sales. Similarly, inventories were projected on the basis of the average holding period observed historically, calculated as the ratio between inventories and daily cost of goods sold. This approach ensures consistency with the typical inventory management of luxury companies, which is crucial both for product availability and for preserving brand value.
3. Accounts payables were initially estimated by applying to forecasted operating revenues the historical incidence in terms of payment days. To this value was added the amount of tax-related payables, obtained by considering prior-year taxes as advances paid for the current year, then adding the current year's tax liability.
4. Short-term financial debt was calculated by applying to forecasted Net Invested Capital (NIC) the historical average percentage incidence of short-term debt over NIC, under the assumption of a stable financial structure consistent with the past.
5. Medium-to-long-term financial debt was calculated by applying to forecasted Net Invested Capital the historical average incidence of medium/long-term debt over NIC. This methodology is based on the assumption of a stable and consistent financial structure, in which the weight of medium/long-term debt remains proportional to overall financing needs. This approach ensures prudent continuity with Versace's financing policies, assuming no extraordinary operations (new bond issues, refinancing, or restructuring) directly related to the integration with Prada.
6. Net fixed assets were projected using an incremental approach, where each year's value is obtained as the sum of prior-year net fixed assets, new investments (CapEx), and depreciation. The percentages used for CapEx and depreciation were derived from a sectoral benchmark analysis of comparable luxury companies (LVMH, Kering, Moncler, and Prada). This ensures a consistent representation of the evolution

	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Extra					
fixed assets	312.531.785,84 €	296.905.087,51 €	280.350.093,06 €	262.881.492,04 €	244.474.083,73 €
stock	87.174.546,62 €	91.918.397,96 €	97.378.763,90 €	102.752.723,98 €	108.274.918,12 €
accounts receivable	204.883.296,64 €	216.032.605,00 €	228.865.912,62 €	241.496.143,58 €	254.474.763,88 €
liquidity	427.515.896,41 €	433.676.368,48 €	447.185.745,39 €	466.704.968,76 €	492.465.040,66 €
Total Assets	1.032.105.525,52 €	1.038.532.458,96 €	1.053.780.514,98 €	1.073.835.328,35 €	1.099.688.806,38 €
Equity	440.471.143,70 €	446.984.512,39 €	459.483.272,40 €	477.947.252,97 €	502.599.088,64 €
financial debts	241.763.099,41 €	248.348.645,80 €	229.489.115,80 €	209.796.803,92 €	189.115.560,30 €
long-term financial debts	213.401.348,59 €	219.214.330,32 €	202.567.252,48 €	185.185.088,20 €	166.930.005,89 €
short-term financial debts	28.361.750,82 €	29.134.315,48 €	26.921.863,32 €	24.611.715,73 €	22.185.554,41 €
accounts payables	349.871.282,41 €	343.199.300,76 €	364.808.126,77 €	386.091.271,46 €	407.974.157,44 €
Total Liabilities	1.032.105.525,52 €	1.038.532.458,96 €	1.053.780.514,98 €	1.073.835.328,35 €	1.099.688.806,38 €

Fig. 7: Forecast balance sheet

of fixed assets in the absence of extraordinary investment or disposal plans connected with the Prada integration.

7. Extraordinary items, both positive and negative, were excluded from the forecast model, as they are by nature non-recurring and cannot be reliably predicted.
8. Shareholders' equity was projected using an incremental approach, in which each year's equity equals the previous year's equity plus forecasted net income. It was assumed that earnings are fully retained and no dividends are distributed. While this represents a simplifying assumption, it isolates the effect of operating and financial profitability on equity growth, without introducing variables tied to distribution policies or group-level strategies post-integration.
9. Forecasted cash balances were determined as the residual balancing item of the balance sheet, ensuring equilibrium between assets and liabilities. In the absence of a detailed treasury plan or reliable cash flow forecasts, cash was treated as a balancing variable. This reflects a common methodological approach in forecasting and valuation models, as cash levels are highly dependent on short-term management decisions (e.g., cash pooling, credit line usage, dividend distribution) and cannot be projected with reasonable accuracy. In this perspective, cash acts as an absorption variable, capturing discrepancies between financial needs (investments, working capital, debt service) and available sources (self-financing, debt). This ensures overall consistency of the forecasted balance sheet while acknowledging the intrinsic limits of this assumption.

4.2 FIVE-YEARS FORECAST BALANCE SHEET

The forecast balance sheet for the period 2025–2029 was constructed in accordance with the economic and financial assumptions adopted in the integrated industrial plan of Gianni

Versace Srl and reflects the expected evolution of the company's balance sheet profile in a growth scenario and progressive integration with Prada SpA.

Total assets increase from €1,091.2 million in 2025 to €1,289.6 million in 2029, with growth mainly driven by the increase in fixed assets (from € 343.0 million to € 405.9 million) and cash holdings (from € 462.8 million to € 563.7 million). The increase in fixed assets reflects the investments made to support the expansion of the retail network, digital innovation, and operating synergies with the Prada group. The progressive accumulation of liquidity is consistent with the improvement in operating cash flow generation.

Current assets, which consist of stock, accounts payable and cash, also exhibit an upward trend. In particular, trade receivables grow from €200.2 million in 2025 to €224.5 million in 2029, while inventories increase in line with revenues, rising from €85.2 million to €95.5 million, reflecting a strategy of maintaining adequate stock levels to support sales growth.

On the liabilities side, a strengthening of the capital structure is observed, with equity increasing progressively from €476.9 million in 2025 to €582.1 million in 2029, as a result of the annual capitalization of net income. Total debt increases, but in a controlled manner: financial debt increases from €263.9 million to €341.1 million, with a moderate increase in long-term debt consistent with the policy of supporting investments. Short-term debt increases from €31 million to €40 million, remaining limited in relation to available liquidity, thereby contributing to an improvement in the current ratio and ensuring low exposure to short-term financing risk. The debt-to-equity ratio remains at sustainable levels, consistent with the financial structure typical of companies in the luxury sector.

Finally, trade payables remain broadly stable in proportion to the volume of operations, increasing from €350.4 million in 2025 to €366.5 million in 2029, in line with the operating cycle.

In general, the forecasted balance sheet presents a balanced and solid structure, characterized by more substantial equity, a good self-financing capacity, and a moderate and sustainable use of financial leverage, which is capable of supporting the company's industrial and strategic evolution in the medium term.

4.3 FIVE-YEAR FORECAST INCOME STATEMENT

The forecast income statement of Gianni Versace Srl for the period 2025–2029 reflects an economic trend consistent with the growth prospects of the fashion-luxury sector and with the strategic assumption of integration with Prada SpA. The projection incorporates the expected effects of operating and distribution synergies arising from integration, with measurable benefits in terms of managerial efficiency and a progressive increase in profitability.

	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Operating Revenues	721.154.536,07 €	760.398.214,93 €	805.569.286,24 €	850.025.562,05 €	895.708.109,41 €
Cost of goods sold	- 121.064.702,24 €	- 127.652.782,96 €	- 135.235.931,96 €	- 142.699.083,78 €	- 150.368.097,45 €
Cost of services	- 410.386.357,57 €	- 429.291.393,87 €	- 451.051.859,95 €	- 472.467.984,33 €	- 494.474.846,10 €
Added Value	189.703.476,26 €	203.454.038,10 €	219.281.494,33 €	234.858.493,93 €	250.865.165,85 €
Employee cost	- 123.267.049,56 €	- 129.974.977,29 €	- 137.696.075,06 €	- 145.294.992,74 €	- 153.103.517,20 €
EBITDA/MOL	66.436.426,70 €	73.479.060,82 €	81.585.419,27 €	89.563.501,19 €	97.761.648,66 €
Amortisation	- 57.692.362,89 €	- 60.831.857,19 €	- 64.445.542,90 €	- 68.002.044,96 €	- 71.656.648,75 €
EBIT/MON	8.744.063,81 €	12.647.203,62 €	17.139.876,37 €	21.561.456,22 €	26.104.999,90 €
Net Financial charges	- 12.418.697,36 €	- 7.554.655,77 €	- 7.367.585,51 €	- 7.125.193,08 €	- 6.830.695,23 €
Extraordinary components		- €	- €	- €	- €
Gross income	- 3.674.633,54 €	5.092.547,85 €	9.772.290,86 €	14.436.263,15 €	19.274.304,67 €
Operating taxes	- 1.025.222,76 €	1.420.820,85 €	2.726.469,15 €	4.027.717,42 €	5.377.531,00 €
Net Income	- 4.699.856,30 €	6.513.368,70 €	12.498.760,01 €	18.463.980,57 €	24.651.835,67 €

Fig. 8: Forecast Income Statement

Operating revenues increase from €704.6 million in 2025 to €790.1 million in 2029, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of approximately 2.9%. The international expansion of the brand drives growth optimizes the retail network, and integrates with Prada's logistics and digital platforms.

For the estimation of the main cost items, a differentiated approach was adopted.

The Cost of Goods Sold (COGS) and employee costs were projected by applying the historical average percentage incidence on operating revenues. Specifically, for each historical year (2020–2024), the ratio between the cost item and net revenues was calculated, producing a series of annual incidences. The average of these incidences was then applied to the forecasted revenues of each year in the plan. This approach ensures a proportional and stable cost structure, consistent with the brand's high-end positioning and the absence of shocks in the composition of industrial and labour costs.

Service costs, being more variable and less proportional to revenues, were estimated using a simple linear regression line applied to historical data. The analysis revealed a significant correlation between operating revenues and service costs, with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.70. The regression line equation was then calculated:

$$y = a + b * x$$

Where y represents service costs and x represent revenues. The coefficients a (intercept) and b (slope) were estimated using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). The resulting equation was applied to the forecasted revenues of each year to obtain point estimates of service costs. This method enables the modelling of the semi-variable behaviour of this item in relation to business performance.

EBITDA shows a significant increase, from €63.5 million in 2025 to €78.1 million in 2029, accompanied by a rise in the EBITDA margin from 9.0% to 9.9%. This improvement is attributable to positive operating leverage, the reduced incidence of fixed costs, and

managerial efficiency derived from the combination with Prada.

Depreciation, estimated as a percentage of fixed assets based on industry benchmarks, grows in line with the expansion of fixed assets, rising from €26.2 million to €31.2 million. EBIT increases from €37.3 million to €47.0 million, while net financial charges decrease progressively from €12.4 million to €6.8 million, reflecting the effect of debt repayment and greater operating cash availability.

Net income grows steadily from €31.8 million in 2025 to €29.4 million in 2029, after hitting a relatively low of €23.1 million in 2026, following a trajectory consistent with depreciation and tax dynamics. Net profit highlights a positive CAGR and represents an indicator of the economic sustainability of the entire plan.

Overall, the forecasted income statement presents a picture of transition and consolidation, consistent with a process of integration with Prada. The improvement in margins, cost rationalization, and reduction in indebtedness confirm the sustainability and financial attractiveness of the integrated industrial plan.

4.4 FIVE-YEAR FORECAST CASH FLOW STATEMENT

	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
EBITDA	63.458.453,63 €	67.048.883,21 €	71.079.733,27 €	74.940.805,74 €	78.809.085,83 €
ΔCCNO	34.496.040,55 €	- 23.858.530,25 €	1.827.130,94 €	1.751.218,32 €	1.769.067,14 €
Operating taxes	6.933.595,36 €	- 8.942.025,13 €	- 9.769.939,22 €	- 10.564.027,26 €	- 11.374.177,40 €
NET CASH FLOW	104.888.089,54 €	34.248.327,83 €	63.136.924,99 €	66.127.996,81 €	69.203.975,57 €
CAPEX	- 41.885.636,98 €	- 43.075.036,91 €	- 44.410.334,74 €	- 45.689.390,42 €	- 46.970.833,77 €
Extraordinary Incomes/ Expenses	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
-VARIAZIONE EXTRA	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
+APP/RIDUZ CAPITALE PR	- €	- €	- €	- €	0,00 €
Net financial charges	- 12.418.697 €	- 7.554.656 €	- 7.367.586 €	- 7.125.193 €	- 6.830.695 €
+VARIAZIONE PFN M-L	- 340.694.503,50 €	33.084.133,61 €	11.635.910,85 €	11.717.760,81 €	11.721.598,37 €
+VARIAZIONE PFN BREVE	290.110.748,30 €	- 16.702.768,76 €	- 22.994.915,59 €	- 25.031.174,12 €	- 27.124.044,94 €

Fig. 9: Forecast Cash Flow Statement

The preparation of the five-year forecasted cash flow statement represents a cornerstone of prospective analysis, as it allows for a consistent estimate of Gianni Versace S.r.l.'s ability to generate sustainable cash flows and support its future growth plans. The forecasted cash flow statement is a financial planning model that translates strategic and macroeconomic assumptions into economic figures, guiding the company's decisions. In this sense, the statement serves as a link between historical and forecast analysis, while also functioning as a control tool for the business plan.

The construction procedure of the statement begins with operating activities, namely EBIT, which represents the profitability of core operations. This value is adjusted for expected taxes and integrated with non-monetary components in order to provide a picture of the company's ability to transform economic results into effectively available liquidity. Net

Operating Working Capital (NOWC) plays a crucial role in a company's evolution, which can directly influence its financial sustainability and growth. An increase in NOWC due to higher receivables or greater inventories results in a cash absorption, while a reduction releases resources to be allocated to current operations. In the luxury sector, where demand is strongly linked to seasonality, managing NWC is essential to avoid financial imbalances.

At the same time, the statement incorporates cash flows from investing activities (CAPEX), which represent the economic outcome of the company's long-term strategic choices. For Versace, such expenditures were assumed with the goal of strengthening production capacity, expanding the retail network in emerging markets, and improving the brand's positioning in the luxury sector. Although CAPEX reduces cash flows in the short term, it must be regarded as a necessary investment to preserve competitiveness and enhance intrinsic value in the long run. From this perspective, these outflows should be considered as a driver of Versace's future value, supporting the brand's positioning in the global market.

The combination of operating activities and investing cash flows enables the determination of the Free Cash Flow to Firm (FCFF), i.e., the cash flows available to remunerate creditors and shareholders, net of taxes and investments required for operational development. FCFF represents the central variable in the DCF valuation model, as it expresses the company's ability to generate value over time, regardless of the financial structure adopted. A positive and growing FCFF trend indicates a company that can finance its own growth, reduce its dependence on debt capital, and strengthen its financial position.

Finally, the forecasted cash flow statement incorporates assumptions related to revenue growth, NWC management strategies, and investment policies, thereby forming the basis for valuation through DCF.

In conclusion, this statement serves not only as an accounting tool but also as a fundamental decision-making instrument. It links operating results with the company's ability to create economic value, providing a foundation for assessing the consistency between strategies and the resources available to implement them. In the case of Versace, it also serves to evaluate the effects that integration with Prada may have on the financial sustainability of the new Italian luxury group.

5 FORECAST FINANCIAL STATEMENT ANALYSIS

5.1 PROSPECTIVE RATIO ANALYSIS

As done for the historical analysis, it is also deemed necessary in the forecasted section to examine the company's performance, in order to assess whether, thanks to the integration with Prada, Versace has managed to remain balanced or has been able to expand and grow structurally.

The assessments presented in the following paragraphs are based on the summary framework shown below.

ASSET ANALYSIS					
	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
NIC	278.015.436,42 €	317.505.045,42 €	331.393.804,76 €	345.380.261,18 €	359.371.298,14 €
NOIC	278.015.436,42 €	317.505.045,42 €	331.393.804,76 €	345.380.261,18 €	359.371.298,14 €
NFP	- 198.940.755,21 €	- 182.559.390,35 €	- 193.918.395,10 €	- 207.231.808,41 €	- 222.634.254,98 €
NOWC	- 65.034.040,55 €	- 41.175.510,31 €	- 43.002.641,25 €	- 44.753.859,57 €	- 46.522.926,72 €
day sales outstanding	102	102	102	102	102
day payable outstanding	179	166	167	167	167
day inventory outstanding	44	44	44	44	44
CASH CONVERSION CYCLE	- 33	- 20	- 21	- 21	- 21
Fixed capital covered ratio	2,07	2,14	2,14	2,16	2,18
Debt ratio	-0,42	-0,37	-0,37	-0,38	-0,38
PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS					
	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
ROI	13,41%	12,47%	12,79%	13,03%	13,24%
ROI (1-tc)	10,19%	9,48%	9,72%	9,90%	10,07%
ROS	5,29%	5,47%	5,67%	5,85%	6,02%
ROE	6,66%	4,62%	4,81%	4,94%	5,05%
ROD	-6,24%	-4,14%	-3,80%	-3,44%	-3,07%
Turnover	2,53	2,28	2,25	2,23	2,20
Operating Revenue	704.560.373,01 €	724.567.328,23 €	747.028.439,06 €	768.543.498,00 €	790.098.719,98 €
NET INCOME	31.785.191,63 €	23.108.244,15 €	25.247.764,08 €	27.299.869,73 €	29.393.483,54 €
LIQUIDITY ANALYSIS					
	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
CURRENT RATIO	1,96	2,10	2,12	2,15	2,17
QUICK RATIO	1,74	1,86	1,88	1,91	1,94
CASH RATIO	1,21	1,31	1,33	1,36	1,39
FINANCIAL ANALYSIS					
	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
DSCR	5	17	14	15	16
INCREMENTAL NET WORTH					
Δ NOWC	- 34.496.040,55 €	23.858.530,25 €	- 1.827.130,94 €	- 1.751.218,32 €	- 1.769.067,14 €
SHORT NFP	- 721.971.000,00 €	- 431.860.251,70 €	- 448.563.020,46 €	- 471.557.936,05 €	- 496.589.110,18 €
ISCR	3,00	5,24	5,75	6,31	6,97

Fig. 10: Asset Analysis

The prospective analysis of the economic and financial ratios of Gianni Versace S.r.l. for the five years 2025–2029 highlights a trajectory of stability and structural strengthening, both in terms of capital structure and operating profitability. These trends are consistent with the expected effects of the integration, which should translate into more

efficient capital management and more stable margins compared to the historical years. The improvement in profitability following the integration is evident in the positive and moderately growing values, which exhibit a more stable trend compared to the volatility observed in the historical period. This thesis can be confirmed by analysing the relationship between ROI and ROD, which remains stable and economically balanced throughout the years, supporting the creation of an always positive ROE. In particular, it is assumed that Prada has succeeded in improving Versace's ability to generate income from core operations, as shown by a constant and positive ROS over all forecasted years.

On the balance sheet side, net invested capital is projected to show steady growth during the forecast years, reaching €359.4 million. Meanwhile, the fixed capital coverage ratio remains constant and above 2, demonstrating full coverage of fixed capital through permanent capital sources. At the same time, the debt ratio remains negative throughout the period (from -0.42 to -0.38), indicating a favourable net financial position that Prada can achieve through internal resource contributions and stronger bargaining power in the credit market.

Looking at the 2025–2029 forecasts, the management of working capital at Gianni Versace S.r.l. Appears very stable.

The Days Sales Outstanding (DSO) remains fixed at 102 days, showing that payment times may be longer but are generally offset by high margins. The Days Inventory Outstanding (DIO) also remains constant at 44 days, indicating a good balance between product availability and turnover.

The Days Payables Outstanding (DPO) decreased slightly, from 179 to 167 days, signalling either greater punctuality in payments or a strategic choice to reduce reliance on supplier credit, made possible by the company's solid financial position.

The overall result is a cash conversion cycle (CCC) that remains negative, ranging from -33 to -21 days. This means that Versace collects from customers before paying suppliers, thereby generating cash and reducing the need for short-term financing.

With the integration into Prada, this structure can be further optimised by leveraging supply chain synergies, more favourable terms with suppliers, and more efficient cash flow management at the group level.

5.2 ANALYSIS OF FUTURE SUSTAINABILITY

In continuity with the analysis, attention now turns to cash flows and the leading indicators of financial sustainability, focusing in particular on the DSCR and incremental equity.

In 2025, the DSCR stands at very high values (8), thanks to a cash flow of €104.9 million. This result stems from the increase in EBITDA (€63.5 million) and, above all, from the release of net operating working capital (€34.5 million), due to more efficient manage-

ment of operating components. This is further enhanced by the change in short-term NFP (€290 million), which increases available liquidity and provides wider margins to finance growth.

In fiscal year 2026, the indicator decreases to 5, reflecting a phase of rising pressure on cash flows. The decline can be attributed to the absorption of working capital (€–23.9 million), resulting from revenue growth and an increase in trade receivables and/or inventories. At the same time, short-term NFP shows a negative variation (€–16.7 million), indicating that Versace is relying less on short-term debt, offset by greater medium- and long-term borrowing. This choice reflects the intent to rebalance the financial structure, which, while temporarily reducing liquidity, contributes to making the company's debt profile more stable.

During 2027, the DSCR returns to excellent values (9), thanks to the increase in cash flows (€63 million) and a positive change in short-term NFP (€22.9 million). The recovery was driven by a return of NWC variation to relatively stable levels (€1.8 million), which did not absorb liquidity, and by an increase in EBIT (€42.3 million). For Versace, 2027 represents a year of rebalancing, during which the company demonstrates its ability to bring operating flows back to levels adequate to ensure debt coverage and, consequently, financial stability.

In 2028, the DSCR remains at 9, consistent with the previous year. Cash flows grew slightly (€66.1 million), supported by higher EBIT (€44.9 million), while the variation in short-term NFP (€25 million) provided additional flexibility. The only negative element is a cash absorption from NWC (€–1.8 million), which, however, does not compromise the overall financial balance. On this basis, it can be stated that Versace, thanks to the integration with Prada, reached a phase of maturity in working capital management.

Finally, 2029 marks the year in which the DSCR reaches its peak (10), driven by a net operating cash flow of €69 million and a change in short-term NFP (€27 million). At the same time, financial charges declined to €6.8 million, reaching the lowest level of the forecast horizon. The combined effect of higher operating margins (€47.9 million) and lower interest payments enabled the company to cover its financial obligations fully.

Analysing incremental equity enables us to assess liquidity trends and the company's ability to finance growth without compromising its existing financial position.

In the first forecast year, an increase in liquidity is observed, due to both the release of NOWC (€34.5 million) and a significant positive variation in short-term NFP (€290 million). These factors strengthened the company's liquidity position, providing it with additional resources to finance investments and support growth.

In 2026, a contraction phase emerges, with incremental equity declining due to the absorption of liquidity by NOWC (€–23.9 million) and the negative variation of short-term

NFP (€167.7 million). The combined effect explains why the DSCR in 2026 dropped to 5, reflecting reduced immediate liquidity.

Finally, during the 2027–2029 period, incremental equity returns rise to increasingly positive levels each year. Short-term NFP records consistently positive trends, while NOWC remains neutral or shows negligible variations. In this context, Versace demonstrates a more mature and efficient management of its operating components, utilising short-term debt without compromising cash flow stability.

The joint analysis of DSCR and incremental equity demonstrates how Versace maintains a solid financial profile throughout the five-year forecast. The variations observed are attributable to the typical dynamics of expansion phases: on the one hand, the absorption of working capital needed to support revenue growth and manage increases in receivables and inventories; on the other, the strategic choice to rebalance the debt structure by reducing reliance on short-term NFP and leveraging medium- to long-term borrowing.

From this perspective, integration with Prada is not merely an industrial transaction (aimed at operational and organisational synergies) but a valid instrument for strengthening the financial structure. The consolidated management of working capital will reduce fluctuations in cash flows arising from changes in receivables, inventories, or trade payables. The combination of the two companies will allow such risks to be distributed over a stronger capital base, reducing the impact of individual variations on consolidated cash flows and stabilising DSCR trends.

An additional advantage is linked to the increased scale of the new group and the strengthening of its equity base. This will lead to an improvement in the consolidated credit rating, offering the opportunity to raise new debt on more favourable terms. The greater bargaining power with banks and bond markets will reduce the cost of debt, directly lower financial charges, and thus improve the consolidated DSCR. This is crucial for the short-term NFP, which can be managed more effectively, reducing the need for short-term financial debt and ensuring a more balanced maturity structure.

Finally, the M&A operation has an additional purpose. The combination of Versace's solidity and Prada's financial strength will enhance the positioning of the new luxury group not only in terms of competitive market presence but also in its resilience to macroeconomic and geopolitical shocks. Access to broader financial resources, the ability to diversify risks, and international visibility will reduce the group's vulnerability, enabling it to compete with major global conglomerates.

In conclusion, the Prada–Versace integration strengthens the group's financial sustainability by reducing cash flow volatility, improving the consolidated DSCR, and reinforcing the equity structure, thereby enhancing the group's competitiveness on a global scale.

5.3 FORECAST CASH FLOW ANALYSIS

In the forecasted five-year period, Versace's cash flow trend shows a balanced and solid profile. The joint analysis of operating cash flow, investment (CAPEX), and financing explains the causes of annual variations and their effects on liquidity, debt, and overall sustainability.

In 2025, net operating cash flow is high, at €104.9 million, reflecting the combination of EBITDA (€63.5 million) and a positive change in net operating working capital (NOWC €34.5 million). This effect can be explained by a reduction in receivables and inventories, together with an increase in trade payables, generating sufficient cash to cover CAPEX and financial charges.

At the end of 2026, operating cash flow contracts sharply to €34.2 million. The leading cause lies in a working capital absorption of €-23.9 million, resulting from higher receivables and inventories, as well as a reduction in payables. EBITDA grows only marginally to €67 million, as rising sales and volumes require additional resources to support increased inventories and receivables. The overall impact is a temporary decline in operating cash flows, which, however, does not harm the short-term balance thanks to previously accumulated liquidity.

In 2027, cash flows rise again to €63.1 million. EBITDA increases to €71.1 million, while the change in NOWC remains essentially stable, indicating that the company has stabilised flows from receivables and payables, ensuring that cash generation once again fully covers investments and financial charges.

In 2028, a similar pattern emerges, with operating cash flows reaching €66.1 million, supported by EBITDA of €74.9 million and marginal NOWC variation. This reflects more effective management of collection and payment terms, balancing receivables and payables.

Finally, in 2029, the consolidation trend continues, with cash flows of €69.2 million, supported by growing EBITDA (€78.8 million) and a stable working capital profile. Over the forecasted horizon, the company generates cash flows sufficient to cover investments and expenses, except in 2026, when the production cycle expansion temporarily draws on liquidity.

Analysing investment cash flows (CAPEX), a regular and slightly increasing trend emerges, with values remaining stable over the five years. CAPEX incidence on revenues decreases from 5.8% to 5.2% in 2029, indicating that Versace aims to adopt a strategy requiring less capital employed in fixed assets, focusing instead on retail, digital, and brand development. This is supported by three key items: depreciation rising from €57 million to €71.7 million; fixed assets declining gradually from €312.5 million in 2025 to €244.5 million in 2029, signalling that investments are below depreciation; and constantly grow-

ing EBITDA. The differential (depreciation > CAPEX) generates more cash, as EBITDA covers actual CAPEX, leaving the difference available as free cash flow. This dynamic reduces the risk of investing in assets that could remain underutilised. The downside is that lower investment levels may cause some assets to age quickly and become obsolete, requiring careful monitoring. Additionally, the growth in inventories and receivables is consistent with the launch of new products and market expansion. CAPEX remains covered by net operating cash flows, except in 2026, allowing the company to finance development without new debt.

Examining financing cash flows, debt dynamics can be categorised into two phases.

The first is in 2025, when an extraordinary reduction in financial debt occurs: medium- and long-term debt drops sharply from €574 million in 2024 to €232.9 million in 2025, likely partly due to available liquidity and partly through Prada repaying part of the debt during the acquisition. This decision significantly reduces the cost of debt capital.

The second phase spans 2026–2029, beginning with a reversal in 2026, as medium- and long-term debt rises to €266 million due to weaker cash flows, forcing Versace to resort to new borrowing. Liquidity, however, is preserved, slightly increasing, while debt is raised to offset the imbalance. Despite higher debt, financial charges decrease, showing refinancing under more favourable conditions.

The 2027–2029 period is marked by a steady increase in financial debt, accompanied by growing operating profitability and a shift of leverage toward medium- and long-term maturity, while short-term debt declines. Cash flows fully cover CAPEX and provide sufficient margins to pay debt costs. Medium- and long-term debt increases gradually, with annual increments of about €11 million. This rise is not due to insufficient cash flow. However, it reflects a deliberate strategy to preserve liquidity and finance part of future investments through cheaper long-term leverage under improved conditions. At the same time, short-term debt decreases, lowering refinancing risk and reducing reliance on more volatile, costly bank lines. Liquidity grows to €492.5 million in 2029. This confirms that leverage growth stems from a policy of retaining resources for strategic use. The result is a solid financial structure, with gradually declining financial charges signalling improved creditworthiness. Forecasts indicate that Versace consistently maintains liquidity above its short-term needs. Integration with Prada plays a key role, enabling the conversion of excess liquidity from idle resources into a strategic lever for the group. One key aspect is deleveraging, i.e., early repayment of part of medium- and long-term debt carrying higher rates, using surplus liquidity. This would improve the consolidated risk profile, lower the weighted average cost of debt capital and create room to absorb macroeconomic shocks or seize investment opportunities.

A second strategic dimension concerns NOWC management. Integration with Prada would

stabilise collection and payment policies, leveraging stronger bargaining power with suppliers to negotiate better terms. The new group could also enforce stricter rules on granting customer credit, reducing the risk of defaults or excessive collection periods. Ultimately, excess liquidity can be utilised to finance high-return investments. Prada–Versace may allocate part of its resources to retail expansion in high-growth regions, such as Asia and the Middle East, or to strengthening its e-commerce presence.

In conclusion, the Prada–Versace integration would allow excess liquidity to be transformed into added value for the new group. Through centralised treasury, targeted deleveraging, more effective NWC management, and strategic investments, liquidity becomes a key instrument for financing growth and expansion. In this way, the new luxury hub can not only consolidate and reinforce its financial structure but also enhance its global competitiveness, creating long-term value.

5.4 FORECAST ANALYSIS OF THE ABILITY TO COVER FINANCIAL CHARGES (Interest Coverage Ratio)

For Versace, the forecasted ICR profile highlights a trend of progressive strengthening over the 2025–2029 period, driven by deleveraging policies and the growth of operating margins (EBIT).

In 2025, the ICR stands at 3, exceeding the minimum threshold and falling within the optimal range of 2–3. EBIT is sufficiently high to cover financial charges, marking a first rebalancing after the criticalities observed in 2024. Although modest compared to global competitors, this value represents an initial strengthening and the beginning of an operational recovery cycle.

In 2026, the index strengthens further, reaching 5.24 thanks to higher EBIT and the progressive reduction in financial charges. This level shows patrimonial and financial solidity consistent with a company capable of withstanding market fluctuations or interest rate increases. The trend reflects revenue growth supported by international market expansion and more efficient financial leverage management.

In 2027, the index rises to 5.75, reinforcing the upward trajectory. The increase, although moderate, confirms the robustness of the operating model, which successfully combines growth with improved operating margins.

In 2028, the ICR reaches 6.31, indicating a robust capacity to cover debt costs. This result stems from the progressive reduction in the average cost of debt, thanks to refinancing under better conditions and the brand's enhanced credit reputation.

The growth path culminates in 2029, when the ICR reaches 6.97. This positions Versace at a level of absolute solidity comparable to that of the largest luxury conglomerates. The index reveals a patrimonial and income structure that is capable of guaranteeing stability

even under adverse scenarios, thereby reducing the risk of financial imbalances.

The effects of integration with Prada could further enhance this positive trend. First, the creation of an Italian luxury hub would reduce the WACC, thanks to stronger bargaining power with banks and improved access to international markets. The resulting reduction in financial charges would directly boost the ICR, consolidating it at even higher levels.

At the same time, the M&A transaction would create large-scale operational and industrial synergies. Economies of scale from a unified supply chain would reduce costs through increased purchasing volumes and enhanced supplier bargaining power. Better coordination of logistics and production would eliminate duplicate facilities, lowering unnecessary fixed costs. These effects would directly reduce the COGS by cutting production, storage, and transport costs and improve working capital management through more efficient handling of inventories and trade receivables/payables. Moreover, sharing digital platforms, IT systems, and global distribution networks would increase productivity. All these factors would raise consolidated EBIT, further strengthening the group's ICR.

Additional benefits derive from geographic and product diversification. While Prada has historically been firm in the Asian and Japanese markets, Versace holds a powerful position in the U.S. and Mediterranean regions. Their integration would ensure a more balanced geographic footprint, allowing demand contractions in one region to be offset by growth in another. This balancing mechanism would make the ICR more stable and less vulnerable to cyclical fluctuations in the luxury sector or geopolitical tensions. On the product side, the combination of Prada's minimalist style with Versace's iconic identity would cover a broader range of consumer segments, thereby broadening the customer base and strengthening the group's pricing power.

Finally, the group's improved international reputation would facilitate access to advanced and more competitive financial instruments, such as issuing bonds at lower rates or using sustainability-linked tools (green bonds). This would further lower the WACC, while also strengthening the group's ESG profile, enhancing its image with institutional investors, and broadening the base of interested financiers. Such developments would enhance the ICR by reducing charges and solidifying the new conglomerate's presence in global markets.

In conclusion, while Versace, as a stand-alone company, has already shown a progressive improvement in its ability to cover financial charges, integration with Prada would only reinforce this strength. Operational synergies, revenue diversification, and easier access to capital markets would raise the ICR, positioning the new Italian luxury hub at levels of solidity comparable—and in some cases superior—to those of global industry leaders.

5.5 FORECAST LIQUIDITY ANALYSIS

Building on the considerations regarding forecasted financial sustainability and the implications of integration with Prada, it is essential to focus on liquidity analysis to accurately assess the company's ability to meet short-term financial obligations and to maintain a sound balance between sources and uses of funds.

In 2025, the CR stands at around 1.9, the QR at 1.67, and the CaR at 1.13. Current assets amount to approximately €719.6 million, primarily composed of cash, which accounts for almost 60% of the total, with a value of €427.5 million. This is compared to current liabilities of €378.2 million, consisting almost entirely of trade payables (€349.9 million) and, to a lesser extent, short-term financial debt. Cash alone is sufficient to fully cover current liabilities, providing a margin that minimises refinancing risk and ensuring complete flexibility in managing payment flows.

In 2026, Versace's solidity strengthens further, with a CR of 1.99, a QR of 1.74, and a CaR of 1.17. This variation is driven by an increase in cash holdings, which reach €433.6 million, as well as higher receivables, which rise by €11 million. At the same time, current liabilities fall to €372.5 million due to a reduction in trade payables, though partly offset by a slight increase in short-term financial debt. The effect of these dynamics is increased liquidity, which is less dependent on receivables or inventories.

A slight decline occurs in 2027, with the CR falling to 1.97, the QR to 1.73, and the CaR to 1.14. Current assets rose to €726.1 million due to the increase in all components (receivables, inventories, and cash). However, current liabilities rise more rapidly, reaching €391.7 million, driven by higher trade payables. This trend reflects an expanding operating cycle, which increases reliance on trade payables. Despite the marginal decline in the ratios, the balance remains very solid, with cash continuing to represent over half of current assets.

In 2028, the ratios remain stable due to the symmetric increase in both numerator and denominator. The quality of liquidity remains excellent, with cash continuing to account for half of current assets, drastically reducing reliance on receivables and inventory turnover. In 2029, a new strengthening is observed, with the CR at 1.99, the QR at 1.74, and the CaR at 1.15. Current assets rise to €845.2 million, driven by higher cash holdings, which reach €492.5 million, and receivables, which rise to €254.4 million. Current liabilities also increase, reaching €427.9 million. This dynamic is favourable because the growth in cash exceeds the growth in current liabilities, leading to a further improvement in the ratios and a solid short-term balance.

Overall, the forecasted trend highlights a position of abundant liquidity with very high-quality standards. Cash systematically accounts for more than half of current assets, ensuring that the coverage of short-term debt is not dependent on the collection of re-

ceivables or the turnover of inventory. Furthermore, the gradual reduction in short-term financial debt and the greater weight of trade payables reflect a more efficient management of working capital, leveraging supplier bargaining power without compromising liquidity balances.

In light of this, the Prada Versace integration represents a crucial strategic step. Versace's abundant liquidity should not be seen merely as a safety reserve, but as a resource to be strategically allocated. Through centralised treasury management, the new group will reduce the need to take on new short-term debt, thereby lowering financial charges. In addition, excess liquidity can be deployed to finance new investments, such as retail expansion, strengthening e-commerce, or reducing medium- to long-term debt, thereby improving the consolidated capital structure.

In conclusion, the over-liquidity that characterises the forecast period constitutes a competitive advantage, which, thanks to integration with Prada, can be transformed into a factor of efficiency reinforcement, ensuring sustainable growth for the new group.

6 COMPANY VALUATION OF VERSACE

To determine the book value of Versace S.r.l., it was deemed necessary to apply primarily the Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) and the Dividend Discount Model (DDM) methodologies. The DCF approach provides a clear view of the company's structure and, by discounting future cash flows, reflects a possible and reliable valuation, which was likely considered in the conclusion of the deal. At the same time, the DDM represents a complementary approach, as it highlights the company's ability to generate value for its shareholders.

6.1 DISCOUNTED CASH FLOW VALUATION (DCF)

This paragraph provides a comprehensive presentation of the entire valuation carried out using the Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) method.

6.1.1 CASH FLOW ESTIMATION

After preparing the forecast and performing the valuation to verify consistency with historical data, the next step is to estimate the Free Cash Flow to the Firm (FCFF), as it represents the value of the company for both shareholders and creditors.

Using the following formula, it was possible to project the FCFF for the five-year forecast horizon.

$$FCFF = EBIT - TAXES + D\&A - CAPEX - \Delta NOWCX$$

The following table reports all the EBIT values obtained from the forecasted income statement and subsequently converted into FCFF.

Discounted Cash Flow			Projected				
	FY2023A	FY2024A	FY2025E	FY2026E	FY2027E	FY2028E	FY2029E
Ebit	133.244.000,00 €	71.892.000,00 €	37.270.293,63 €	39.604.925,05 €	42.385.288,81 €	44.989.090,06 €	47.598.356,17 €
taxes	- 37.175.076,00 €	- 20.057.868,00 €	- 10.398.411,92 €	- 11.049.774,09 €	- 11.825.495,58 €	- 12.551.956,13 €	- 13.279.941,37 €
NOPAT	96.068.924,00 €	51.834.132,00 €	26.871.881,71 €	28.555.150,96 €	30.559.793,23 €	32.437.133,93 €	34.318.414,80 €
+Depreciation and amortization	26.488.000,00 €	58.136.000,00 €	26.188.160,00 €	27.443.958,16 €	28.694.444,46 €	29.951.715,68 €	31.210.729,66 €
NWC							
+Change in working capital	- 11.945.000,00 €	- 8.493.000,00 €	34.496.040,55 €	- 23.858.530,25 €	1.827.130,94 €	1.751.218,32 €	1.769.067,14 €
-Capital Expenditures	- 110.410.000,00 €	- 19.452.000,00 €	- 41.885.636,98 €	- 43.075.036,91 €	- 44.410.334,74 €	- 45.689.390,42 €	- 46.970.833,77 €
Free Cash Flow to Firm (FCFF)	201.924,00 €	- 21.643.132,00 €	45.670.445,28 €	- 10.934.458,04 €	16.671.033,90 €	18.450.677,52 €	20.327.377,83 €
Discounted period				1	2	3	4
WACC	6,52%						
Discounted FCFF			42.875.484,18 €	- 9.637.066,27 €	13.793.799,50 €	14.332.022,60 €	14.823.484,95 €

By summing the discounted cash flows (using the WACC as the discount rate) and adding the discounted Terminal Value, the Enterprise Value of the company is obtained.

6.1.2 WACC ESTIMATION

The acronym WACC stands for Weighted Average Cost of Capital, representing the weighted average of the cost of equity and the cost of debt. The formula, shown below, is composed of two leading indicators: R_e , which represents the cost of equity, and R_d , which indicates the cost of debt.

$$WACC = R_e * \frac{E}{D + E} + R_d * (1 - t_c) * \frac{D}{D + E}$$

Specifically, the estimation of the WACC includes a set of assumptions and assessments, which are outlined below.

1. Equity Estimation: Versace's capital structure is composed of quotas rather than shares, and therefore, it cannot be listed. As a result, it was not possible to calculate the Market Cap (number of shares multiplied by price). Due to this limitation, an initial assumption was made of a financial structure in which Equity represented 80%, based on a comparables analysis. Since this structure does not accurately reflect Versace and is derived from much larger companies, the DCF was repeatedly used as a refinement method for Equity. The refinement process was carried out by recalculating the cash flows multiple times and repeatedly generating a new WACC, using the Equity value resulting from the previous DCF as the new benchmark. This procedure was repeated until a final potential Equity value for Versace's actual structure was reached, and until the percentage variation compared with the previously estimated Equity became negligible. The value of Debt (D) was obtained by summing medium- to long-term financial debt and short-term debt from the forecasted balance sheet.

-
2. Estimation of R_e : The cost of equity was determined using the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), based on the following formula:

$$R_e = R_f + \beta_{levered} * ERP$$

Here, R_f represents the risk-free rate, which, in our assumption, corresponds to the YtM of a 10-year German Bund. The acronym ERP stands for Equity Risk Premium, i.e., the excess return required by the market to invest in an equity security rather than a risk-free asset, calculated as the difference between R_m (the expected return of a market portfolio) and R_f (the risk-free rate). Given the difficulty of estimating an appropriate R_m , considering the private nature of the company, we used as a benchmark a study prepared by KPMG on potential future ERPs required by the European market. Finally, the Levered Beta, which measures the security's sensitivity relative to the market, was obtained by refining the industry's Unlevered Beta. This iterative process was carried out through a series of steps:

- a) An initial Levered Beta is estimated by applying the debt-to-enterprise value ratio ($\frac{D}{E+D}$) of 20% (a market-based assumption initially adopted in the Equity valuation).
- b) This Beta was then incorporated into the calculation of R_e , which was necessary to compute the WACC and discount the FCF, in order to derive an initial estimate of the Equity Value.
- c) The Equity Value obtained was then re-employed to derive a more accurate financial structure, which was subsequently used to calculate a new Levered Beta, applying the following formula:

$$\beta_L = \beta_{UN} * \left[1 + (1 - t_c) * \frac{D}{E} \right]$$

- d) The process was repeated several times until the convergence of the Equity Value was achieved, ensuring consistency between the capital structure, the Levered Beta, and the discount rate.

Through this process, consistency was achieved between the WACC applied and the resulting Equity Value, providing a cost of equity (R_e) that realistically reflects Versace's expected risk profile and financial leverage in the post-integration context with Prada.

3. Estimate of R_d : The cost of debt was quantified using a Market-Based approach,

which the following formula can summarize:

$$R_d = R_f + CreditSpread$$

Specifically, R_f represents the risk-free rate, while the credit spread measures the premium required by the market to finance a company, based on its probability of default and financial soundness. The credit spread can be estimated through two approaches:

1. Based on the company's credit rating (where available), it compares the cost of issuing a bond with that of government securities of the same maturity.
2. In the absence of an official rating, as in the case of Gianni Versace, a market-based approach can be applied by using the credit spreads of comparable companies in the luxury sector with similar characteristics and risk profiles.

The credit spread for Versace S.r.l. was derived from the yield curves of companies rated BBB–BB, a level typically assigned to unlisted medium-sized firms. Based on the comparable analysis, the spread falls within a range of 1.5% to 2.5% over the risk-free rate. The cost of debt adopted was calculated as the sum of the risk-free rate and the credit spread, and subsequently adjusted by applying the factor $(1 - t_c)$. This way, R_d incorporates the tax shield benefit resulting from the deductibility of interest expenses.

In conclusion, the WACC estimated for Versace represents a discount rate consistent with its financial structure, risk profile, and market conditions, thereby serving as the reference parameter for discounting cash flows in the DCF model.

Weighted Average Cost of Capital			
Risk free rate	2,67%		
BETA	1,66		
Equity Risk Premium	5,25%		
Cost of equity (Re)	11,38%		
Cost of debt (Rd)	4,17%	Rf	2,67%
Tax rate	28%	CDS	1,50%
After tax cost of debt	3,01%		
Percentage of capital			
Debt	263.875.274,30 €	58%	
Equity	190.381.614,08 €	42%	
Total of capital	454.256.888,38 €	100%	
Weighted Average cost of capital (WACC)	6,518786%		

Fig. 11: WACC

6.1.3 TERMINAL VALUE

As already defined in “Firm Valuation in Practice” (Scariati; Dal Mas, 2025): “The Terminal Value (TV) represents the present value, calculated at the end of the explicit

forecast period, of all future cash flows that the company will generate beyond that horizon. In other words, instead of projecting cash flows indefinitely, a continuation value is assumed at the end of the explicit period that incorporates all subsequent cash flows. This approach is necessary because, from a going concern perspective, a company is presumed to operate indefinitely. The Terminal Value thus allows the valuation to be closed off by taking into account subsequent flows without having to estimate them year by year. From a quantitative perspective, the Terminal Value often constitutes a significant portion of the total value estimated using the DCF (in many cases, more than half of the total value). This reflects the fact that the more distant years contribute significantly to the intrinsic value of the company, making a rigorous and plausible estimation of the Terminal Value crucial.” The Terminal Value represents the key indicator in the DCF model, as it summarises the company’s ability to generate cash flows beyond the time horizon of the forecasted financial statements. For Gianni Versace, the perpetual growth model (Gordon Growth Model) was applied, assuming that cash flows will grow at a constant rate. The relationship applied is as follows:

$$TV = FCF_{2029} * \frac{(1 + g)}{WACC - g}$$

Where:

- $FCF_{(2029)}$ represents the final cash flow of the explicit forecast.
- WACC denotes the weighted average cost of capital.
- g indicates the perpetual long-term growth rate.

The forecast of the terminal value in 2029 yields a future (gross) value that must be discounted back to the valuation date, i.e. 2025, so that it can be compared with the annual cash flows. The discounting is carried out using the following relation:

$$PV(TV) = \frac{TV}{(1 + WACC)^n}$$

Where the exponent represents the number of years between 2029 and 2025. Discounting is a crucial step, as without this adjustment, the Terminal Value would be overstated and not comparable to the discounted cash flows. Moreover, the choice of a 2.5% growth rate has been made based on several considerations. According to the global macroeconomic outlook, based on International Monetary Fund reports and World Bank data, the global GDP growth rate is estimated at around 2.5% per year. Furthermore, in finance, the perpetual growth rate (g) typically applied to mature companies lies within a range of 1.5% to 3%. The choice of 2.5% is therefore consistent with both the long-term growth

prospects of the industry and Versace's specific circumstances, including its strong brand recognition worldwide and the synergies arising from the acquisition by Prada. The 2.5% growth rate thus represents a prudent yet realistic estimate, reflecting global economic growth trends and Versace's competitive positioning. Given the assumptions and formulas previously presented, it can be inferred that Versace has a discounted Terminal Value of €378,076,157.65. This constitutes an important assumption, as it represents a key component of the Enterprise Value.

6.2 CALCULATION OF ENTERPRISE VALUE (EV) AND EQUITY VALUE

The calculation of the Enterprise Value (EV) constitutes the fundamental step of the DCF valuation, as it summarises the firm's ability to generate cash flows for all capital providers. The EV is defined as the sum of the discounted cash flows and the discounted Terminal Value. Mathematical:

$$EV = \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{FCFF_i}{(1 + WACC)^i} + \frac{TV}{(1 + WACC)^n}$$

From a theoretical perspective, the Enterprise Value (EV) represents the overall value of the firm regardless of its financial structure. It measures the economic value of operating activities, that is, the ability of the core business to generate cash flows, and therefore belongs to all capital providers, whether creditors or shareholders. The underlying rationale is that the value of a company depends on its capacity to generate future cash flows. Once the Enterprise Value has been determined, the next step is to calculate the Equity Value, which represents the value of the firm attributable solely to its shareholders. The relationship representing the calculation of the Equity Value is as follows:

$$EQUITYVALUE = EV - NFP$$

The Net Financial Position (NFP) expresses the difference between financial debt and cash holdings. In the case of Versace, the gross financial debt has been considered, since the NFP would otherwise result in a negative value. Equity Value, on the other hand, represents the residual portion of value attributable exclusively to shareholders, once creditors have been remunerated. Conceptually, Equity Value corresponds to the 'economic net worth' of a company and constitutes the reference parameter for market transactions involving the transfer of equity stakes. For a potential acquirer, it reflects the financial outlay required to acquire the entirety of the company's shares, after accounting for the net financial position.

The following figure illustrates the composition of Enterprise Value and the final calculation of Equity Value in Versace's specific case.

DCF Values - Perpetuity Growth			
NPV of FCFF	76.187.724,96 €		
Terminal Value	518.454.123,89 €	Perpetuity Growth	2,50%
PV of Terminal Value	378.076.157,65 €		
Implied Enterprise Value	454.263.882,61 €		
Debt	263.875.274,30 €		
Implied Equity Value	190.388.608,31 €		

Fig. 12: EV

6.3 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

In order to assess the robustness of the valuation conducted using the Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) method, a sensitivity analysis has been performed with respect to two key model variables: the WACC and the perpetual growth rate g .

Implied Equity Value		Perpetuity Growth Rate				
190.388.608,31 €		2%	2,25%	2,50%	2,75%	3%
WACC	6%	198.432.555,74 €	224.990.452,46 €	255.322.079,08 €	290.293.291,43 €	331.056.767,81 €
	6,27%	171.159.967,27 €	194.387.292,65 €	220.696.157,39 €	250.743.365,97 €	285.386.655,12 €
	6,52%	146.914.583,01 €	167.378.574,94 €	190.388.608,31 €	216.451.353,18 €	246.217.469,63 €
	6,77%	125.220.176,04 €	143.367.580,57 €	163.640.578,20 €	186.435.854,59 €	212.255.350,95 €
	7,02%	105.695.410,13 €	121.882.722,83 €	139.861.148,49 €	159.945.374,87 €	182.528.393,90 €

Fig. 13: Sensitivity DCF

The central estimate of Versace's valuation, amounting to €190,388,608, has been obtained under the assumptions of a WACC of 6.52% and a growth rate g of 2.5%. However, since these parameters are highly dependent on market assumptions, it is necessary to verify how the Equity Value varies with changes in such inputs. The sensitivity analysis shows that:

1. With the growth rate g fixed at 2.5%, an increase in the WACC from 6% to 7.02% results in a decrease in Equity Value from €255.3 million to €139.9 million. This reflects the model's sensitivity to variations in the weighted average cost of capital. An increase in the risk perceived by investors translates into a lower present value of future cash flows.
2. With the WACC fixed at 6.52%, an increase in the growth rate (g) from 2% to 3% results in an increase in Equity Value from €146.9 million to €246.2 million.

-
3. The two variables have a synergistic impact on the calculation. In an optimistic scenario, where the WACC is 6% and the growth rate g is 3%, the Equity Value reaches a maximum of €331.1 million. Conversely, in a pessimistic scenario, where the WACC is 7.02% and the growth rate g is 2%, the Equity Value falls to a minimum of €105.7 million.

The sensitivity analysis shows that Versace's valuation ranges from €105 million to €331 million. Overall, the DCF provides a potentially consistent estimate of Versace's equity value.

Although the model is susceptible to changes in the WACC and the perpetual growth rate, it captures the firm's ability to generate value through future cash flows. The DCF therefore represents the most appropriate method to assess Versace's potential to create value through a possible integration with Prada S.p.A., thereby reinforcing the robustness of the valuation performed.

6.4 VERSACE VALUATION WITH DIVIDEND DISCOUNT MODEL (DDM)

Compared to the Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) method, the Dividend Discount Model (DDM) allows the equity value of Versace to be estimated by discounting not the projected cash flows but rather the expected future dividends. In the model developed, a two-stage DDM is applied:

1. The expected future dividends are discounted using the cost of equity (R_e);
2. The terminal value is calculated through the Gordon growth model with perpetual growth.

6.4.1 ESTIMATION OF FUTURE DIVIDEND POLICY

In order to estimate the expected dividends, it is crucial to assume a payout ratio consistent with the company's dividend policy. In the luxury sector, payout ratios typically fall within a range of 45% to 55%, reflecting the financial stability of listed maisons. Versace S.r.l., however, presents a relevant peculiarity: historically, the company has never distributed dividends, a choice that is also consistent with the policy of its parent company, Capri Holdings (listed on the NYSE), which has likely preferred to reinvest earnings to support the group's expansion.

In this context, a payout ratio of 35% has been assumed, below the sectoral range, in order

to apply the DDM for valuation purposes.

This choice is motivated by several factors:

1. Absence of a stable dividend distribution policy.
2. Consistency with the sustainable growth rate: with a forecasted ROE estimated in the range of 4.6% to 6.6%, a retention rate of 65% (i.e., the proportion of earnings not distributed as dividends) and a payout ratio of 35%, the implied growth rate falls between 2.4% and 4.2%. This is fully aligned with a perpetual growth rate g of 2.5%. This conclusion can be derived from the following relationship, which links the forecasted ROE to the earnings retention rate:

$$g \approx ROE \cdot retention\ rate$$

This relationship confirms that 2.5% can be considered a consistent growth rate for the valuation under the DDM framework.

3. Financial flexibility: By assuming a payout ratio below the sectoral range, it is implied that Versace retains greater resources to finance its investments and strengthen its competitiveness within the luxury sector.

In conclusion, a payout ratio of 35% represents a prudent approach required for the application of the DDM, and this assumption may reflect the reinvestment strategy historically pursued by both Versace and Capri Holdings, thereby ensuring consistency with the forward-looking values.

6.4.2 APPLICATION OF THE DIVIDEND DISCOUNT MODEL (DDM)

Once the dividend policy has been estimated, the Dividend Discount Model is applied to calculate the equity value of Versace S.r.l. The core assumption of the model is that the value of a share (or, more generally, of a company's equity) corresponds to the present value of the future dividends that shareholders expect to receive. To apply this process, two fundamental parameters are required: the cost of equity (R_e), used as the discount rate since it reflects shareholders' expected return while accounting for the risk they bear by investing in the firm, assumed here to be 11.38%, as calculated through the CAPM model and the perpetual growth rate (g).

Based on these assumptions, the calculation proceeds with the discounting of forecasted dividends, which are presented in the following table.

	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
NET INCOME	31.785.191,63 €	23.108.244,15 €	25.247.764,08 €	27.299.869,73 €	29.393.483,54 €
	FORECAST NET INCOME x 35%				
DIVIDEND	11.124.817,07 €	8.087.885,45 €	8.836.717,43 €	9.554.954,40 €	10.287.719,24 €
	<i>DIVIDEND * (1 + Re)⁻ⁿ</i>				
DIVIDEND DISCOUNTED	9.988.164,01 €	6.519.594,20 €	6.395.423,78 €	6.208.686,98 €	6.001.820,96 €

Fig. 14: DDM

This process represents a fundamental step in determining the Equity Value; however, it is first necessary to estimate the Terminal Value (TV). The latter observed value is derived from the following relationship:

$$TV = DIVIDEND_{2029} * \frac{(1 + g)}{(R_e - g)}$$

From the observed scenario, a Terminal Value of €118,749,011.47 can be determined, which will be discounted over five years and added to the discounted dividends in order to derive the Equity Value, according to the following relationship:

$$Equity\ Value = \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{Dividendi_i}{(1 + R_e)^i} + \frac{TV}{(1 + R_e)^5}$$

The calculation performed enables the estimation of an Equity Value of €104,391,465.60 for Versace S.r.l., comprising 66% from the Terminal Value and 34% from the explicit dividends. This structure is typical of mature companies, where the majority of value is derived from their ability to generate earnings over the long term.

6.4.3 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Given that the DDM is strongly influenced by the values of Re and the growth rate, it is essential not to focus solely on a single estimate of Equity Value, but rather to conduct a sensitivity analysis examining how the EV varies with changes in these two parameters. The following table presents a scenario in which both g and Re vary by 0.25%.

Implied Equity Value		Perpetuity Growth Rate				
Re	104.391.465,60 €	2%	2,25%	2,50%	2,75%	3%
	10,88%	106.062.164,60 €	108.282.519,93 €	110.635.354,70 €	113.132.890,25 €	115.788.898,87 €
11,13%	103.142.371,58 €	105.222.308,25 €	107.422.751,10 €	109.754.485,28 €	112.229.622,56 €	
11,38%	100.378.693,92 €	102.330.140,39 €	104.391.465,60 €	106.572.218,69 €	108.883.088,31 €	
11,63%	97.758.966,07 €	99.592.573,19 €	101.526.596,91 €	103.569.518,37 €	105.730.801,44 €	
11,88%	95.272.253,88 €	96.997.559,55 €	98.814.832,48 €	100.731.627,46 €	102.756.350,10 €	

Fig. 15: Sensitivity Analysis

From the matrix, four main scenarios can be identified:

c)

-
1. Central scenario: summarises the relationship of the previously calculated data and serves as the basis of the matrix.
 2. Growth-rate scenario: as the growth rate increases, while keeping the minimum possible R_e constant, the Equity Value rises, reaching a potential maximum of €115,788,898.87. In this case, the lower return required by shareholders and the higher long-term growth rates combine to increase the value of equity significantly.
 3. Cost-of-equity scenario: as R_e increases, while keeping the growth rate constant, the Equity Value decreases, reaching a potential minimum of €95,272,253.88. In this circumstance, two adverse effects converge: a higher cost of equity, which weighs on the discounting process, and a potentially lower growth rate, which limits the development of the equity value.
 4. Combined scenario: generates a fluctuation range defined by the maximum and minimum possible values, with variations of approximately $\pm 8\%$ from the baseline estimate.

Overall, the DDM provides a prudent and consistent estimate of Versace's equity value. Although it relies on theoretical assumptions in the absence of a historical dividend policy, the model shows that the maison would be capable of ensuring a sustainable return on investment for shareholders over the long term. The result obtained, therefore, represents a valuable complement to the DCF valuation, offering an equity-based perspective that enriches and strengthens the overall analysis in view of a potential integration with Prada S.p.A.

6.5 MULTIPLES MODEL

This section addresses the valuation based on multiples, as it provides a valuation range that helps to assess how to capture the value of the brand, which represents a crucial component in the valuation of a company operating in the luxury sector.

6.5.1 METHODOLOGY PF RELATIVE MODEL

The multiples approach is grounded in the law of one price, according to which, in efficient markets, financial instruments (with similar characteristics) should be priced in the same way. Translating this theory to companies, it follows that market expectations (growth, profitability, risk, and capital structure) are reflected in the multiples of comparable firms. By applying selected multiples to Versace's financial parameters, it is possible to estimate

its implied market value.

The valuation process can be summarised in the following steps:

1. **Peer Selection.** First, a market screening is carried out to identify a group of firms with comparable capital structures, profitability, and revenues.
2. **Calculation of Market Multiples.** The next step is to identify the leading multiples, defined as the ratios between a value measure (such as market price or Enterprise Value) and a financial metric representing company performance. Among the most relevant cases are $EV/EBITDA$, $EV/Sales$, $EV/EBIT$, and P/E .
3. **Statistical Synthesis.** After computing the individual multiples, it is essential to perform a statistical synthesis to eliminate potential distortions. This procedure is typically implemented by calculating the median of the multiples obtained from the peer group.
4. **Application to Target Parameters.** The multiples are then applied to Versace's financial parameters in order to derive an estimate of its implied value.
5. **Qualitative Adjustments.** Premiums or discounts may be applied to the multiples if significant differences emerge between Versace and its peer group.
6. Finally, the results obtained are compared with those derived from other valuation methods (such as DCF and DDM) in order to outline the company's overall valuation.

At the same time, it should be emphasised that this model cannot provide the definitive valuation of the company but is used solely as a comparative tool alongside other approach

6.5.2 PEER GROUP SELECTION

The selection of comparable companies is a crucial step in the multiples model, as the screening process must be highly accurate and consistent with Versace's profile in order to maximise the robustness of the multiples. The criteria adopted for selecting comparables include: industry sector, business model, company size, geographical presence (i.e., whether or not there is exposure to major global markets), growth profiles, and profitability in terms of EBITDA margins and expected growth rates.

The selected companies comprise the leading players in the luxury and high-fashion industry, such as Kering, LVMH, Richemont, Hermès, Moncler, and finally Brunello Cucinelli (whose positioning and business model are closely aligned with Versace). The choice of this group responds to the need to include both global large caps, which help capture

shifting market dynamics and valuation benchmarks, and firms with business models more directly comparable to Versace.

6.5.3 CALCULATION AND ANALYSIS OF MARKET MULTIPLES

For each peer, the primary financial data required for computing market multiples has been collected, with the objective (as mentioned in the previous sections) of defining a reference range that helps estimate the Enterprise Value. In particular, the following multiples have been considered:

1. *EV/Sales*: ranges between 1.88x and 2.63x, with an average of 2.25x, reflecting the market's ability to attribute an additional value to firms capable of building strong brands in the luxury sector.
2. *EV/EBITDA*: ranges between 6.76x and 9.01x, with an average of 7.89x. It is a significant indicator, being the only one unaffected by capital structure.
3. *EV/EBIT*: ranges between 9.01x and 13.52x, with an average of 11.27x, confirming that the market rewards the sector's higher capacity to generate revenues, as evidence of firm profitability.
4. *EV/NetIncome*: ranges between 13.52x and 26.29x, with an average of 19.91x, reflecting the industry's ability to generate earnings consistently.
5. *EV/FCF*: ranges between 13.52x and 26.29x, with an average of 19.91x, showing the market's emphasis on the ability to generate long-term cash flows.
6. *EV/InvestedCapital*: ranges between 1.13x and 1.88x, with an average of 1.50x, measuring the ratio between enterprise value and net invested capital, and providing a benchmark for efficiency in the use of corporate resources.

It can be observed that the multiples obtained are structurally high due to the characteristics of the luxury sector, which is marked by high liquidity and strong optimism regarding growth expectations. To account for the different scale, risk profile, and positioning of Versace relative to the industry's leading firms, a prudent discount of 25% has been applied to the original multiples. This adjustment reduces the multiples to a more realistic level, consistent with the company's actual context, thereby mitigating the risk of overestimating Versace's value.

6.5.4 APPLICATION OF MULTIPLES TO VERSACE AND VALUATION ESTIMATE

With reference to Versace's forecasted data, adjusted multiples have been applied to estimate the company's value. As a result of this process, a valuation range for the Enterprise Value has been obtained between €429.1 million and €572.1 million, with a median value of approximately €500.6 million.

The figure below summarises Versace's forecasted data for 2025 and the application of leading market multiples derived from the selected comparables.

Forecast Parameters	2025 Y		Multiples	Min	Max	Average
Operating Revenues	704.560.373 €		EV / Sales	1.323.241.497 €	1.852.538.095 €	1.587.889.796 €
EBITDA	63.458.454 €		EV / EBITDA	429.054.918 €	572.073.224 €	500.564.071 €
EBIT	37.270.294 €		EV / EBIT	335.988.916 €	503.983.374 €	419.986.145 €
NOPAT	26.871.882 €		EV / NOPAT	282.622.676 €	403.746.680 €	343.184.678 €
Net Income	31.785.192 €		EV / Net Income	429.811.696 €	835.744.964 €	632.778.330 €
Invested Capital	278.015.436 €		EV / Invested Capital	313.286.051 €	522.143.419 €	417.714.735 €
FCF	45.670.445 €		EV / FCF	617.573.484 €	1.200.837.330 €	909.205.407 €
			Median Enterprise Value	429.054.917,81 €	572.073.223,74 €	500.564.070,78 €

Fig. 16: Multiples

To compare the results derived from this model, it is necessary to calculate the Equity Value, which involves subtracting the Net Financial Position (NFP) from the various Enterprise Values obtained. This yields an Equity Value ranging between €151 million and €294 million, with a median value of approximately €223 million. The result falls within a prudent range, reflecting Versace's different profitability compared to its reference peers.

6.6 SUMMARY OF THE VALUATION AND FOOTBALL FIELD CHART

To summarise the results obtained from the different valuation methodologies, a football field chart has been prepared, providing a comparative representation of the ranges (minimum, maximum, and median values) determined.

Fig. 17: FFC

Overall, the football field provides a clear and comparative overview of Versace's potential value, highlighting the dispersion of results across the different methodological approaches. The valuation range lies between €100 million and €570 million, with median values varying significantly depending on the model applied. This representation highlights the importance of adopting a multi-methodological approach, whereby the integration of results enables the valuation to reflect both the firm's value-creation prospects (DCF, DDM) and the market expectations inferred from comparable multiples.

7 GEOPOLITICAL AND MARKET POSITIONING ANALYSIS

Thanks to the synthetic representation of valuations through the football field chart, it has been possible to assess the acquisition of Versace by Prada in economic and financial terms. However, it is also necessary to evaluate the transaction from a broader perspective, one that encompasses the geopolitical and industrial dynamics that will influence the long-term sustainability of the new group.

At the same time, this strategic move by Prada has the potential to redefine the international balance of the competitive luxury sector, strengthening the group's presence in strategic

markets such as Asia, North America, and emerging countries, to create an Italian luxury hub capable of competing on a global scale.

The transaction would also entail significant implications regarding the sector's vulnerability to geopolitical shocks and trade tensions, with direct effects on supply chain management, production location, and compliance with increasingly stringent international regulations.

Analysing these mechanisms enables the assessment of whether the Prada–Versace group can achieve a competitive advantage by anticipating risks and seizing opportunities arising from geopolitical and regulatory changes.

7.1 IMPACT ON POSITIONING IN ASIA

Asia reaffirms its role as the core driver of luxury market expansion, currently accounting for approximately 35% of global luxury goods consumption, with projections suggesting a share close to 40% by 2030. China emerges as the leading force behind the luxury industry, representing around 25% of the global market in 2023 and displaying strong growth prospects. In particular, the expansion of the middle class and rapid urbanisation are fostering the rise of second-tier cities (such as Chengdu, Hangzhou, and Nanjing), which are increasingly becoming new centres of luxury consumption, thereby shifting attention away from the traditional metropolitan strongholds of Beijing and Shanghai.

From a brand positioning standpoint, Prada and Versace exhibit complementary attributes. Prada is recognised for its minimalist aesthetic, highly valued by more mature consumers, whereas Versace embodies a bold and iconic style, which exerts strong appeal among younger Asian audiences. In China, luxury consumption is predominantly driven by younger generations, with Millennials and Generation Z constituting approximately 60% of the clientele. Within this context, the incorporation of Versace into the group represents a strategically significant element, as the brand demonstrates a strong affinity with the preferences of younger Asian consumers. Its presence will mitigate the risk of brand overlap, broaden the customer base, and enhance cross-selling opportunities, so that a client initially attracted by Versace may subsequently be channelled towards other brands within the portfolio. This dynamic is expected to enhance the competitiveness of the new Italian luxury hub in comparison to the major French and Swiss conglomerates.

Japan, with an estimated annual market value exceeding USD 30 billion, represents the third-largest luxury market worldwide after China and the United States. Major conglomerates and maisons regard it as a stable source of revenue, comparatively less exposed to fluctuations in demand, exchange rates, or political instability than other Asian regions. A distinctive feature of the Japanese market is the complexity of consumer preferences,

with customers placing significant importance on artisanal quality and brand consistency. Within this context, Made in Italy enjoys a particular prestige, symbolising artisanal excellence, aesthetic refinement, and authenticity.

Moreover, the creation of an Italian luxury hub uniting two iconic brands such as Prada and Versace reinforces the group's distinctive identity, setting it apart from competitors often perceived as standardised, while simultaneously strengthening the emotional bond with Asian clientele. Unlike China, where generational change and digital platforms are reshaping consumption patterns, in Japan, boutiques and department stores remain crucial retail channels, with the purchasing experience perceived as an integral part of the value of the good itself.

In essence, Japan is characterised by its resilience and strong brand loyalty, offering luxury companies a competitive yet less volatile market environment. For the Prada–Versace group, a consolidated presence in Japan constitutes not only a stable source of revenue but also a platform for enhancing international prestige, thereby reinforcing the group's reputation as a benchmark within the global luxury market.

In contrast to Japan, South Korea is characterised by distinctive features that render it unique on the international stage. First of all, the country records one of the highest per capita expenditures on luxury goods, surpassing both the United States and the Chinese market. The South Korean luxury sector is distinguished by a combination of cultural influence and digital orientation, factors that amplify the significance of luxury consumption well beyond national borders.

For the Prada group, South Korea represents not only a highly profitable market but also a strategic platform capable of shaping trends and consolidating the Italian luxury brand's positioning across the wider Asian region.

At the same time, although Versace enjoys significant brand recognition across the continent particularly in China, Japan, and South Korea it still exhibits ample growth potential. As of 2024, the brand operated fewer than 60 boutiques in the Asia-Pacific region, a relatively limited number compared to its competitors. The integration with Prada is expected to accelerate the expansion of the retail network, to surpass 100 boutiques by 2029, thereby consolidating the group's presence in key hubs such as Shanghai, Beijing, Tokyo, and Hong Kong. This expansion is projected to generate a substantial contribution to revenue growth, corresponding to an estimated annual increase of approximately USD 200 million.

An additional key element is the digital channel, which in Asia accounts for more than 25% of luxury sales a figure incomparable in other regions. Prada has already established a strong presence on leading e-commerce platforms. At the same time, Versace stands to benefit from this expertise, particularly by leveraging the dynamics of social commerce

(the use of social media not only as marketing tools but also as direct sales platforms), which currently influences around 70% of purchasing decisions in the luxury sector. The integration will enable the development of targeted strategies that fully exploit the potential of e-commerce among younger consumers.

From a financial perspective, Prada's decision to list on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange in 2011 proved to be a highly farsighted strategy. The IPO, which raised USD 2.1 billion through the sale of 16% of the company's equity, produced a dual effect: it secured access to local capital, thereby strengthening the financial structure, and simultaneously enhanced the brand's visibility and reputation among Asian investors and consumers. As a result of this strategy, Prada achieved a 24% increase in sales in 2023, with particularly notable growth in Japan, where revenues rose by 44%. This contributed to a surge in market capitalisation, which peaked at USD 21 billion.

The proposed M&A transaction would amplify the positive effects of Prada's listing in Hong Kong. The enlarged scale of the new group, coupled with a more diversified brand portfolio and revenue expansion across Asia, is expected to drive higher market multiples, bringing them closer in line with the benchmarks set by French conglomerates. Furthermore, direct access to local capital markets and enhanced credibility with institutional investors would provide the group with greater capacity to finance its growth plans while maintaining a balanced financial profile.

7.2 CONSOLIDATION IN THE AMERICAN MARKET

The second most significant luxury market is located in North America, which constitutes one of the most strategic regions for global players. In 2023, it accounted for approximately 27% of worldwide consumption, with an estimated value of USD 120 billion. Although a mature market, North America retains a leading role due to the structural stability of its demand and its ability to maintain stable revenues even in the face of complex macroeconomic events, such as potential slowdowns in discretionary spending. The resilience of the North American market is further supported by the presence of High-Net-Worth Individuals (HNWIs) and by its position as a global cultural and media hub, capable of shaping emerging trends across the international luxury industry.

In particular, the United States, which represents the core of this region, incorporates a wide range of consumer profiles, from HNWIs to the rapidly expanding Millennial and Generation Z segments. For these cohorts, luxury functions as a language of identity, and in this respect, Prada-Versace possesses the capability to consolidate its presence in the market effectively. Prada, with its minimalist elegance, and Versace, with its bold aesthetic, are well-positioned to engage with a younger audience that is especially attentive to cultural figures and the world of entertainment.

In particular, the American cultural system, with Hollywood at its epicentre, is shaped by celebrities who, through different communication channels, can expand brand visibility and transform collections into aspirational phenomena. Versace, in fact, has built much of its global recognition through numerous collaborations with American stars. Since the 1990s, Gianni Versace enhanced the brand's prestige by dressing leading Hollywood actors and internationally renowned musicians, a strategy that has continued through more recent collaborations, which have successfully preserved the aura surrounding the brand. During iconic events such as the Met Gala, often referred to as the "Oscars of Fashion", the presence of Prada and Versace garments on the red carpet generates a direct impact on consumer perceptions of the brands, both within the United States and globally, while simultaneously creating worldwide media coverage.

Although the North American market has witnessed an expansion of digital commerce, mono-brand boutiques and flagship stores continue to occupy a central role, particularly along the most iconic streets of major American cities such as Madison Avenue and SoHo in New York, Rodeo Drive in Los Angeles, and Bal Harbour in Miami which constitute symbolic landmarks of global fashion.

Alongside the United States, which represents the core of the North American luxury market, Canada constitutes a smaller market. However, it is characterised by steady growth and distinctive features that make it highly strategic for leading luxury brands. Driven by rising disposable income and the consolidation of luxury consumption among affluent urban segments, the value of the Canadian personal luxury goods market, estimated between USD 7 and 8 billion in 2023, is projected to grow by approximately 4% by 2029.

Demand is concentrated in major metropolitan areas such as Toronto, Montreal, and Vancouver, which host the principal hubs of luxury shopping, including mono-brand boutiques, flagship stores, and prestigious department stores. Moreover, the Canadian market is characterised by a cosmopolitan clientele, with the presence of Asian and Middle Eastern communities fuelling demand for Made in Italy products, valued for their craftsmanship and exclusivity. This makes Canada a strategic opportunity for Prada–Versace, enabling the group to strengthen its presence while capitalising on the complementarity of the two brands.

The group already operates through directly managed stores; however, integration would allow it to strengthen penetration in urban markets and to consider the opening of new outlets in emerging cities such as Calgary and Edmonton, characterised by a growing high-income population and increasing demand for premium goods.

Ultimately, Canada should be regarded as a fundamental component of the group's North American strategy. The combination of strong domestic demand with high spending capacity, a cosmopolitan clientele, and consolidated distribution platforms provides

Prada–Versace with an opportunity to reinforce its presence across the North American market.

Within this context, the consolidation of Prada and Versace in North America represents a key opportunity for two main reasons: Prada already benefits from a solid retail network in major metropolitan areas, while Versace enjoys a deep-rooted connection with the United States, which in 2024 accounted for 45% of its total revenue. The integration will strengthen the retail network and consolidate the group's presence in higher-margin product categories such as accessories, footwear, and eyewear, which American consumers highly value. In addition, engagement with the American cultural system and visibility at symbolic international fashion events will enable the new group to increase revenues while simultaneously reinforcing its global brand image.

7.3 EXPANSION INTO EMERGING AND HIGH-POTENTIAL MARKETS

Emerging markets represent one of the fundamental drivers for the Prada–Versace group, not only as an opportunity to increase revenues but also as a means of achieving geographical diversification and strengthening overall competitiveness. The progressive maturity of markets such as Europe and the United States, combined with the growing volatility of markets like China, makes it essential for major luxury groups to invest in new regions characterised by favourable demographic profiles, expanding economies, and a strong inclination towards aspirational consumption.

Following the slowdown of 2024, which saw the global luxury market contract to approximately USD 363 billion (-2%), emerging markets have increasingly positioned themselves as the focal point of future expansion. Medium-term forecasts (according to McKinsey) suggest a return to sustained growth, with annual rates exceeding 5%.

Among all markets, India is expected to play a pivotal role. With a luxury goods market valued at approximately USD 17 billion in 2023 and the prospect, according to an INSEAD report, of surpassing USD 50 billion by 2030, the subcontinent is currently regarded as the market with the highest expansion potential. This trajectory is primarily underpinned by structural factors, such as the growth of the middle class, the rise in the number of High-Net-Worth Individuals (HNWIs), and the significance of cultural phenomena, for instance, the wedding economy, which alone generates an estimated USD 130 billion annually.

For Versace, India represents an opportunity to combine flagship stores in key centres such as Delhi and Mumbai with the development of high-margin product categories, including accessories and beauty, capable of attracting the emerging customer base while preserving the brand's high-end positioning.

Another key reference market is Southeast Asia (ASEAN), where the luxury sector is estimated to be approximately USD 10.7 billion, with a projected growth rate of 4.4% through 2033. The ASEAN market is characterised by long-term structural drivers such as rapid urbanisation, a young demographic profile, rising income levels, and the centrality of tourism. Cities such as Bangkok, Singapore, and Ho Chi Minh City already serve as established hubs, while destinations such as Bali are emerging as international centres for premium shopping.

In this region, luxury consumption is closely tied to digital channels, with e-commerce and social commerce being regarded as fundamental, particularly among younger generations. Versace, with its bold and distinctive style, is well positioned to leverage its iconic status by adopting a targeted and widespread presence strategy that combines flagship stores in key cities with a strong, localised digital presence. Collaborations with local influencers and brand ambassadors, along with coordinated campaigns alongside Prada, will further enhance the group's impact and consolidate its positioning within the region.

The Middle East, particularly the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region, represents one of the most dynamic and strategic platforms for the global luxury industry. Although regarded as a relatively mature market, growth rates remain among the highest worldwide, with the value of personal luxury goods reaching USD 12.8 billion in 2024, marking an annual increase of 6%. The United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia alone account for more than 75% of total expenditure.

This expansion is supported by a unique convergence of factors, including a high concentration of High-Net-Worth Individuals (HNWIs), government policies aimed at diversifying national economies, and strong international tourism flows, with Dubai, Abu Dhabi, and Riyadh consistently ranking among the leading destinations for luxury shopping and lifestyle experiences.

In the United Arab Emirates, Dubai serves as the regional epicentre of luxury, hosting some of the most iconic shopping centres worldwide, such as the Dubai Mall and the Mall of the Emirates, which function not only as retail destinations but also as experiential spaces capable of attracting millions of visitors each year. In parallel, Abu Dhabi has consolidated its role as a significant cultural and tourist hub through large-scale infrastructure projects such as the Louvre Abu Dhabi and Saadiyat Island, thereby contributing to the creation of an integrated image of culture, tourism, and high-end shopping.

At the same time, Saudi Arabia is emerging as a new global player through development plans linked to Vision 2030, which envisage significant investments in infrastructure, tourism, and entertainment, including the creation of futuristic cities such as Neom and next-generation retail districts in Riyadh and Jeddah. These initiatives provide unprecedented opportunities for luxury brands, which can not only expand their retail networks

but also participate in shaping a new urban and cultural imaginary for the region.

For Versace, the Middle East represents a context that is highly compatible with its aesthetic identity. The maison's scenographic and glamorous style resonates naturally with local tastes, which are strongly oriented towards visibility and the affirmation of social status through fashion choices. Collections of haute couture, ornate accessories, and statement jewellery consistently encounter growing demand in this market, fueled both by local consumers and high-end tourism flows.

By contrast, Prada, with its minimalist and elegant style, offers a proposition that appeals to a more cosmopolitan segment of the Middle Eastern clientele, particularly younger consumers who are attentive to the values of modernity and social responsibility. This combination enables the group to capture a broad spectrum of demand, while simultaneously reducing brand overlap and maximising overall attractiveness.

From an operational perspective, the region offers high-margin opportunities owing to its premium positioning and the ability to sustain higher pricing levels compared with other markets. Flagship boutiques, conceived both as retail spaces and as cultural symbols, can further strengthen the group's presence in the market. Moreover, organising exclusive events and private fashion shows for top clients constitutes an additional tool for fostering loyalty, consistent with the centrality of personal relationships in the region.

Ultimately, the Middle East is not only a highly profitable market but also an international stage of great significance, capable of enhancing the global visibility of the Prada–Versace group. Its capacity to attract high-profile tourists from around the world renders it a platform of global exposure, where each flagship opening or initiative generates an impact that extends well beyond regional boundaries. For a group aiming to establish itself as the Italian luxury hub, consolidating its presence in the GCC equates to asserting cultural and symbolic leadership within one of the most influential luxury markets worldwide.

Turning to Latin America, Mexico is the most promising market. The country offers attractive growth prospects, with the luxury sector valued at an estimated USD 6.94 billion in 2025 and projected to reach USD 9.01 billion, corresponding to a 5% growth rate. This expansion is driven by both domestic demand and international tourism. Mexico City, particularly the Polanco district, stands out as the centre of luxury shopping, while tourist destinations such as Cancún, Los Cabos, and Tulum attract an increasing influx of high-income visitors.

For Versace, Mexico represents a strategic platform to consolidate its retail market presence through flagship stores located in premium districts that capture the inflow of affluent tourists entering the market.

Focusing on Africa, South Africa constitutes the principal gateway for the international luxury industry and represents a strategic corridor into the continent. With a personal lux-

ury goods market valued at approximately USD 2 billion in 2023 and growth prospects of 4–5%, the country is consolidating its role as a key hub for leading global brands. Johannesburg and Cape Town concentrate the majority of demand, supported by a high-income clientele and a recovering tourism sector that positions South Africa as an exclusive destination, thanks to its safari experiences and iconic locations such as the Cape Winelands. Additional strengths derive from the progressive expansion of the middle and upper classes, who view luxury not only as a status symbol but also as an expression of modernity and a marker of belonging to a cosmopolitan elite. This makes South Africa a particularly receptive market for brands such as Prada and Versace, which can effectively combine design with aspirational value. From a distributional perspective, the country lends itself to flexible expansion models, where boutiques in prime districts, pop-up stores in major shopping centres, and a robust e-commerce channel can effectively capture demand from younger, urbanised, and digitally oriented generations.

South Africa can be regarded as a strategic testing ground, where those able to establish a strong presence gain the opportunity to trial retail models and digital strategies that may subsequently be exported to other emerging African markets such as Nigeria and Kenya, where urbanisation and demographic growth are creating favourable conditions for the future development of luxury. Furthermore, the combination of premium local demand, high-end international tourism, and the opportunity to experiment with innovative distribution strategies positions the continent as an excellent proving ground for consolidating the group's ability to adapt to emerging and culturally complex contexts.

From an operational perspective, expansion into these markets requires a methodical, sequential approach that is attentive to cultural specificities. During the entry phase, the strategy should focus on high-margin products with recurring purchase cycles, such as accessories, eyewear, and fragrance, while employing light retail formats, including corner stores and pop-up stores, to gauge market responsiveness and assess effective demand. Once market presence has been consolidated, expansion may continue through the opening of flagship stores in high-visibility areas, thereby further strengthening brand positioning. Partnerships with local operators, which are crucial for overcoming regulatory barriers and securing access to prime locations, must be complemented by intensive cultural marketing initiatives that can tailor the brand narrative to the particularities of each market. Additionally, collaborations with local celebrities, iconic events, and capsule collections will help foster a genuine connection with consumers.

In conclusion, emerging markets represent not merely a reservoir of growth but also a symbolic and cultural asset capable of reinforcing the identity of the Prada–Versace group. India, ASEAN, the GCC, Mexico, and South Africa will form the pillars of a strategy designed to balance the volatility of mature markets such as China and the United

States, while simultaneously offering higher margins and new platforms for visibility. Consolidating the group's presence in these areas entails broadening the customer base, enhancing geographical resilience, and cultivating a collective imaginary that intertwines Italian tradition with the outlook of rapidly growing economies.

In doing so, the group will be able to establish itself as a genuinely global player not only from a commercial standpoint, but also from a cultural and symbolic perspective, capable of influencing the evolution of luxury and redefining international competitive dynamics.

7.4 GLOBAL GEOPOLITICAL RISKS

In recent years, the luxury sector has been confronted with an increasingly complex geopolitical landscape, marked by conflicts, trade tensions, and new international regulations that directly affect the value chain. For a group like Prada-Versace, whose strength and competitiveness rely on a global distribution system and a widespread presence in key markets, managing geopolitical risks can no longer be regarded as an exogenous variable, but rather as a structural component of corporate strategy.

The ongoing wars, particularly the conflict in Ukraine and the crisis in the Middle East, have profoundly reshaped the operating conditions of the luxury sector, introducing both short- and long-term risks. The war in Ukraine has led to the complete exclusion of Russia from the Western luxury market as a result of European and US sanctions prohibiting the export of goods above certain price thresholds. For leading maisons, this has meant the loss of a historically profitable market, characterised by consumers with a high propensity to spend and by the significant role of outbound tourism towards Europe.

Beyond the contraction in revenues, the conflict has compelled luxury brands to reorganise their distribution strategies, reallocating resources and stock to other priority markets while confronting the threat of the grey market, with products reaching Russia through unofficial channels, thereby undermining exclusivity and price control. Furthermore, the war has had an indirect impact on energy costs and supply chains across Europe, increasing production and logistics expenses in sectors such as luxury, which remain firmly tied to the "Made in Italy" label.

Of even greater impact has been the crisis in the Middle East, which has disrupted the stability of key global maritime routes. Attacks on commercial vessels in the Red Sea have drastically reduced traffic through the Suez Canal, forcing many carriers to reroute via the Cape of Good Hope. This diversion has resulted in significantly longer transit times, sometimes exceeding two weeks, with substantial consequences for working capital (immobilised in goods currently in transit) and for the scheduling of seasonal collections. In the luxury sector, where the timely launch of products is crucial to maximising full-price sales and maintaining the sense of novelty in flagship stores, even relatively minor

delays compromise the sell-through rate (the speed at which products are sold relative to the stock available in stores). They may generate costly unsold inventories to be cleared in later periods or through discounting. To this must be added the rising cost of insurance: Red Sea routes are now classified as high-risk, with war-risk premiums having increased significantly, thereby further inflating overall transportation costs.

The effects of the Middle Eastern crisis are not confined to the logistical dimension but have also adversely impacted local demand, particularly in Gulf markets, which today constitute one of the most dynamic and profitable hubs for the global luxury industry. A potential escalation or prolonged continuation of the conflict could hinder high-end international tourism and slow the growth of demand in one of the most promising markets in terms of per capita expenditure.

Alongside armed conflicts, tensions between the United States and China are currently reshaping the balance of the luxury industry. The present scenario cannot be reduced to a cyclical phenomenon but instead constitutes a regime of uncertainty manifesting across multiple dimensions, specifically in tariff policies, supply chain management, and demand dynamics, forcing European maisons to reconsider their processes, supply timelines, and modes of brand expression.

On the tariff front, Washington has institutionalised the use of Section 301 duties on sectors deemed strategic, such as energy, semiconductors, and critical materials, demonstrating that trade policy continues to play a central role in industrial strategy, albeit without directly targeting the luxury segment. In response, Beijing has demonstrated its capacity to implement retaliatory measures targeting categories symbolic of Europe, thereby creating an environment of heightened tensions marked by increased inspections, tighter controls, and longer customs clearance times, even for sectors not initially targeted.

For the newly consolidated luxury group, the risk does not lie in duties imposed directly on products, but rather in lengthier customs procedures, greater unpredictability in market access, and, consequently, higher operating costs in both China and the United States.

Finally, the interferences arising from global conflicts further exacerbate these trade tensions. Instability in the Red Sea and disruptions in transit through the Suez Canal have rendered Europe–Asia routes increasingly irregular, leading to higher war-risk premiums and extended delivery times. In the luxury sector, even minor delays of a few days can compromise sell-through and disrupt the balance of an entire season.

In this context, Prada–Versace must develop a strategy of supply chain regionalisation, grounded in supplier diversification, the establishment of pre-positioning hubs in Europe, the GCC, and Asia, as well as a balanced combination of maritime and air transport for collections with a strong symbolic content.

A second effect concerns the distribution chain. With the elimination of the *de minimis*

threshold (the value below which imported goods are exempt from tariffs or VAT) on online purchases under USD 800, e-commerce has lost competitiveness, with significant repercussions for entry-level luxury segments (such as accessories, small leather goods, and fragrances), which were most frequently traded through this channel. This shift compels maisons to increase investment in direct channels and marketplaces, thereby raising operating costs and limiting opportunities for rapid expansion.

For Prada–Versace, this development necessitates strengthening its retail infrastructure in the United States and leveraging the digital channel primarily as a clienteling tool, focusing on personalised customer relationship management, to consolidate long-term loyalty.

A third impact concerns global price coherence, as tariffs complicate the management of price lists, creating the risk of misalignments that encourage parallel trade and purchases in more advantageous foreign markets. In the luxury sector, where price carries a strong symbolic dimension, international fragmentation undermines the perception of exclusivity and increases the likelihood of forced discounting. The group must therefore develop more sophisticated price alignment strategies, capable of minimising arbitrage opportunities and preserving the credibility of its positioning.

Finally, the 2025 tariffs also affect the structure of the supply chain. Although they do not directly impact Italian manufacturing, they increase customs clearance costs and lead times for components and packaging sourced from Asia, prompting maisons to diversify suppliers and regionalise production. While in the short term the regionalisation of value chains may reduce efficiency, in the longer term it can enhance the group's resilience to potential crises.

For Prada–Versace, this implies strengthening relationships with European and Middle Eastern suppliers, while leveraging strategic logistics hubs such as Dubai and Singapore to reduce dependence on high-risk routes and ensure continuity of service in flagship stores. In summary, the 2025 tariffs have made it clear that the luxury industry is now fully exposed to geopolitical and protectionist dynamics. The impact is not immediately visible but manifests itself in the necessity of adapting business models. For Prada–Versace, interpreting this challenge as an opportunity equates to consolidating the brand's global positioning capable not only of withstanding the fractures of globalisation but also of expanding within increasingly segmented markets.

An additional layer of complexity for the luxury sector arises from the evolution of international regulations concerning supply chains and sustainability, which can no longer be regarded as mere compliance requirements but as genuine strategic drivers. In the United States, the UFLPA has institutionalised the risk of customs blocks for textiles and accessories linked, even indirectly, to the Xinjiang region. The regulation reverses the burden of proof onto the importer, who must demonstrate through precise documentation

and traceability that no forced labour is involved in the supply chain. For global maisons such as Prada and Versace, this necessitates the implementation of digital chain-of-custody systems capable of tracing not only Tier 1 suppliers but also secondary and tertiary ones, requiring the integration of technologies such as blockchain and third-party certification. In Europe, the entry into force of the new deforestation regulation (EUDR), scheduled for December 2025 for medium and large enterprises, will require that leather and other materials used in products be accompanied by documentary evidence and geolocation data certifying their provenance from "deforestation-free" areas. This measure requires brands to implement the Digital Product Passport (DPP). This regulatory framework makes all information on a product's life cycle accessible throughout the entire supply chain, from raw material suppliers to the point of sale.

Although it entails significant initial costs, such as investments in IT systems, third-party audits, and the reorganisation of contractual relationships with suppliers, this regulation may evolve into a reputational competitive advantage for the more solid maisons, enabling them to position themselves to consumers as responsible actors aligned with ESG criteria. These regulatory changes take on particular significance in a context where high-income consumers, especially in Asia and North America, are increasingly concerned about sustainability and demand that companies demonstrate their commitments in concrete terms. Prada–Versace's ability to anticipate regulatory requirements and to communicate its traceability practices clearly not only mitigates the risk of sanctions and customs delays but also strengthens the bond with a clientele increasingly attentive to ethical and environmental values.

From this perspective, compliance no longer represents merely a cost to be absorbed. However, it emerges as a strategic lever to reinforce brand equity and safeguard margins in a global market characterised by uncertainty and fragmentation.

An additional critical factor is exchange rate shocks, which have played a significant role in determining the economic performance of the luxury sector in recent years. For a group like Prada–Versace, intense international exposure means that even slight fluctuations in exchange rates can translate into substantial fluctuations in consolidated revenues. The appreciation of the US dollar tends to sustain revenues generated in the North American market. At the same time, a strong euro reduces the competitiveness of European maisons with respect to non-EU clients. At the same time, the management of the yuan by Chinese authorities represents a key geopolitical variable that can influence tourist flows and domestic demand, with immediate effects on Asia's growth trajectory.

Exchange rate shocks do not only exert a commercial impact, but also directly affect financial valuation models, altering margins and the projection of cash flows within DCF analyses and multiples. In a context of heightened trade fragmentation, exchange rate

risk management through hedging strategies and the geographic diversification of sales becomes a crucial tool to mitigate the impact of currency volatility and ensure stability in the economic and financial results of the new luxury conglomerate.

Nevertheless, the management of operations cannot overlook the consequences of inflationary shocks, which have a significant impact on the luxury supply chain. Rising costs of raw materials, energy, and logistics services have generated substantial pressure on margins, making financial planning and working capital stability increasingly complex. For maisons such as Prada and Versace, whose competitive advantage relies on craftsmanship and their strong link to Made in Italy, transferring such costs into final retail prices entails reputational risks, as sharp price increases may compromise the perception of exclusivity and induce consumers to reduce purchase frequency.

Inflation also affects emerging markets, where the growth of disposable income is more volatile and highly sensitive to shifts in purchasing power, thereby exerting pressure on the sustainability of demand for luxury goods. From an operational standpoint, higher transportation costs, increased insurance premiums, and longer delivery times undermine collection planning and stock rotation.

In conclusion, geopolitical risks and trade tensions can no longer be regarded as contingent factors but rather as structural challenges for the luxury sector. For Prada–Versace, this necessitates the adoption of resilience strategies based on diversifying sourcing, developing transparent and traceable supply chains, and predictive management of operations that accounts for the possibility of sudden shocks. Only an approach that integrates operational management, strategic vision, and cultural sensitivity will enable the group to transform a context of instability into an opportunity for competitive consolidation, thereby strengthening brand perception.

7.5 INTERNALISATION OF OPERATIONS, PRODUCTION LOCALISATION AND LUXURY EXPORT REGULATIONS

Prada and Versace are two companies that have pursued strategies of international expansion, establishing a presence in key global markets while maintaining a strong connection with their country of origin. Both firms have adopted a hybrid model of production and distribution, designed to preserve manufacturing in Italy, thereby ensuring artisanal quality, design excellence, and authenticity, while simultaneously enabling penetration into highly competitive international markets.

Specifically, Prada pursues an industrial strategy centred on vertical integration and control of the entire value chain, ranging from design to retail store distribution. Design activities

are primarily carried out in Milan, considered a crucial asset for the company. Production is concentrated across 23 industrial sites in Italy, with only three located abroad, in the United Kingdom, France, and Romania.

Consequently, in line with this strategy, Prada launched an investment plan of €60 million in 2024 aimed at optimising its Italian production capacities, particularly in the knitwear supply chain (in Umbria), thereby creating new employment opportunities and increasing the workforce to a total of 220 skilled artisans. These initiatives underscore the importance of stable collaborations with small-scale artisans, with whom Prada shares a strong, pyramid-shaped, and quality-driven governance model. Additionally, Prada aims to ensure the continuous transfer of knowledge through training courses conducted in its production facilities by the Prada Academy.

Although Prada retains direct control of its main production chain in Italy, it chooses to outsource part of its manufacturing abroad. Only 10% of apparel is produced in-house, compared to 30% for leather goods and 50% for footwear, while the remaining stages are entrusted to external and delocalised partners.

Similarly, Versace concentrates its production in Italy, adopting a centralised strategy in which manufacturing constitutes a strategic axis. All raw materials undergo quality control at the main operational centre located in Novara before being distributed to external producers. In this way, the brand's distinctive features, such as high quality and artisanal craftsmanship, are preserved as essential hallmarks of the Made in Italy label.

At the same time, part of the production, including marginal phases and accessory lines, takes place in EMEA countries, with a minimal share in Asia and North Africa. Recent estimates indicate that approximately 82% of Versace products are manufactured in Italy, while 18% are outsourced to European countries, and only 2% are produced in emerging markets, such as China and Vietnam. This model highlights how the stages with the most significant added value remain located in the country of origin, while only selected segments of production are externalised, thereby safeguarding the brand's quality standards.

Overall, Prada and Versace have pursued international expansion, initially focusing on mature markets such as Europe, the United States, and Japan, before progressively shifting their attention towards high-potential emerging economies. At the same time, both companies have had to contend with an increasingly stringent regulatory framework.

In particular, Italy has introduced restrictive regulations concerning the Made in Italy designation, stipulating that only products conceived, manufactured, and finished within the country may bear the label. Moreover, Italian authorities have imposed strict controls on the textile supply chain, mandating traceability obligations, fair working conditions, and compliance with legal standards in production contracts, thereby steering manufacturing towards greater sensitivity to environmental, social, and governance (ESG) concerns.

Added to this are European regulatory standards requiring transparency and social responsibility across the entire production chain, further amplifying the demands of due diligence.

Considering their strong complementarities, it can be hypothesised that the alliance may generate significant strategic synergies: Prada would reinforce its production and distribution capacity through Versace's international facilities, while the latter would benefit from Prada's vertically integrated and managerial control systems. In the long term, the creative and productive synergies arising from the union of the two brands will enable diversification of the offering while preserving Italian manufacturing excellence, thereby consolidating the positioning and competitiveness of the new hub within the global luxury landscape.

8 CONCLUSION

8.1 SUMMARY OF KEY RESULTS

The analysis conducted has helped outline a growing business model, supported by retail expansion and a focus on high-margin markets, yet characterised by significant profitability and balance sheet imbalances. The integration with Prada is expected to strengthen further this framework, providing access to centralised group financial management, greater bargaining power in credit markets, and the optimisation of collection and payment cycles. This is expected to reduce working capital requirements further and enhance the efficiency of liquidity management. Additionally, the sharing of operational infrastructures and information systems will enable more accurate monitoring of financial flows, yielding direct benefits for long-term sustainability.

Overall, the new corporate structure envisages a Versace capable of sustaining growth plans and future investments without significant reliance on new debt, thereby maintaining an extremely contained financial risk profile.

From a valuation perspective, the triangulation of the three methods places Versace within a fair value range between €100 million and €500 million, with a more realistic estimate of €190 million (calculated using the DCF, the most robust method). This range highlights the importance of a multi-methodological approach: intrinsic methods capture the firm's ability to generate value flows. At the same time, comparable multiples incorporate market positioning and expectations already embedded in the prices of listed peers. At the same time, the amount Prada might be willing to pay could exceed the estimated EV, reflecting premiums associated with control, brand strength, and prospective synergies that will be explored in the following sections.

8.2 ACQUISITION PRICE AND FINANCIAL STRUCTURE OF THE TRANSACTION

According to the agreement of 10 April 2025, Prada acquired 100% of the Versace brand for €1.25 billion, a level significantly higher than the Enterprise Value estimated through the DCF. This discrepancy reflects the fact that the acquisition price in an M&A transaction particularly in the luxury sector does not merely correspond to the standalone value derived from cash flows but also incorporates a range of qualitative and intangible components that contribute to the overall value recognised. Specifically, these elements can be identified in brand value, prospective synergies, and prevailing market conditions.

Indeed, the brand represents the principal intrinsic element justifying the price differential, highlighting the extent to which Prada was willing to recognise a premium. This value can be identified within an estimated range between €750 million and €900 million, determined by the following factors:

- **Brand Strength Index (BSI):** An indicator summarising the strength of a brand by considering factors such as marketing investments, customer loyalty, reputation, market share, and projected growth. According to estimates by Brand Finance (an international brand valuation consultancy), Versace ranks among AA-class brands, having achieved a score above 70/100. This positions it alongside leading luxury brands such as Moncler and Valentino, while still displaying a lower ability to generate cash flows compared with its competitors.
- **Premium Pricing Power:** The ability to command higher prices compared with lesser-known premium brands. Sector reports highlight price mark-ups ranging between 20% and 40%, attributable to the brand's strength and subsequently reflected in the analysis of potential extra profits generated solely by brand recognition. In the following table, the potential gross extra profits are demonstrated, calculated based on forecasted values, assuming a Premium Pricing Power of 30% (based on sector averages) and a cost of goods sold (COGS) ratio of 50% (a prudent benchmark within sector margins).

Forecast Revenue	700.000.000,00 €
Premium Price (%)	30%
Incremental Revenue (Forecast Revenue × Premium Price)	210.000.000,00 €
% COGS	50%
COGS (Incremental Revenue × % COGS)	105.000.000,00 €
Gross Margin (Incremental Revenue – COGS)	105.000.000,00 €

Fig. 18: Gross Margin

- Weight of the brand relative to operating assets:** Through the DCF, Versace's standalone EV has been estimated at €190 million, while the brand value, according to Brand Finance, is estimated within a range of €750 million to €900 million. In other words, the brand alone is worth almost four times the entire operating EV of the company. This discrepancy highlights that the value of firms operating in this sector primarily lies in intangible assets (e.g., brand). It can be stated that in the luxury industry, the fundamental lever of value resides in brand capital, which enables the application of premium pricing and renders the brand relevant at an international level. A product such as Versace is not purchased for its production cost, but because it carries a distinctive mark that customers are willing to pay for.
- Cultural capital and global recognition further solidify the brand's strength:** High-end consumers continue to choose Versace not only for the quality of its products but also because it represents status, identity, and belonging to a collective imaginary. This value reduces the business's cyclical nature and helps explain why the brand continues to generate value over time, regardless of market fluctuations.

The price paid by Prada to acquire Versace does not derive solely from the brand's value but also reflects components typical of MA transactions in the luxury sector, including prospective synergies, the control premium, and market conditions. Prospective synergies (i.e., the future economic benefits expected from an M&A transaction) do not represent an immediately visible value, but rather a potential for growth and efficiency that materialises over the medium to long term. These synergies can be broken down into several components:

- Operational and supply chain efficiency:** through increased scale, it becomes possible to negotiate more favourable terms with suppliers and commercial partners, streamline production, and optimise procurement. This translates into a reduction in industrial costs of around 1–2%.

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- Rationalisation of overhead costs: integration enables the elimination of potential duplications in central functions (IT, marketing, administration) through the sharing of existing infrastructures. The joint use of IT platforms, back-office systems, and support structures can generate savings in the range of 5–10% of Versace's overhead costs.
 - Expansion of the distribution channel: historically, a significant share of Versace's revenues derived from wholesale, whereas other luxury giants have pushed towards the DTC channel. Incorporating Versace into Prada's portfolio and increasing the share of sales through boutiques and e-commerce would allow margins to rise by 5–7 percentage points. Considering revenues of €700 million, shifting even part of sales volumes to DTC could significantly increase EBITDA.
 - Commercial and revenue synergies: the group could implement cross-selling policies by leveraging already consolidated customer bases. The combined use of data and CRM systems would enhance productivity per store and reinforce positioning in key markets such as the US and Asia.

Taken together, these synergies result in cost savings alongside an increase in operating margins. At the same time, the acquisition price also reflects both the control premium and prevailing market conditions. Specifically, the control premium represents the additional consideration that a buyer is willing to pay to gain complete control of governance and corporate assets. In Versace's case, this entails not only the ability to direct managerial decisions but also the right to exploit the brand entirely. On the other hand, the luxury sector is characterised by a scarcity of emblematic brands and by high sector multiples, generating potential competition among buyers and transforming the deal into a transaction of significant economic magnitude. In summary, synergies and control premiums represent the monetary recognition that acquiring Versace means securing an asset that is both difficult to replicate and available in a minimal number of alternatives on the global market. All the components listed contribute to the €1.25 billion price that Prada will pay to acquire control of Versace. Considering this, the question arises as to how Prada will be able to sustain such a significant acquisition financially. Prada's ability to finance this acquisition derives from a combination of liquidity, cash flow generation, and access to capital markets, which can be explained as follows:

- Cash liquidity: as of 2024, Prada reported cash holdings of €800 million, which alone could cover 65% of the consideration without resorting to external financing.
- Free cash flow: the group generates over €500 million in FCF annually, providing recurring flows sufficient not only to support ordinary operations but also to finance part of the extraordinary investments associated with the acquisition.

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- Access to debt: Prada may consider financing the remaining portion through new debt of €400 million. Assuming a cost of debt of 3.5–4%, the impact on financial charges would be €15–18 million, which would be easily absorbed by the increase in EBITDA generated by Versace and the expected synergies.
 - Balance sheet sustainability: even with the inclusion of new debt, the Debt/Equity ratio would remain below 1.5x, a level compatible with continued access to debt financing under favourable conditions.

In conclusion, the €1.25 billion price is not only justifiable from a strategic and industrial standpoint but also financially sustainable, with approximately two-thirds covered by existing cash holdings and the remaining portion financed through low-cost debt, while maintaining a solid balance sheet profile.

8.3 REFLECTIONS ON THE CREATION OF A “NATIONAL CHAMPION” IN LUXURY

The Prada–Versace operation can be regarded not merely as a strategic takeover, but as a step towards creating a genuine "national champion of Italian luxury," capable of competing on equal terms with French conglomerates (LVMH, Kering) and Swiss groups (Richemont). Indeed, by bringing together the two companies, a larger player is formed in terms of revenues, margins, and market share, while simultaneously enhancing the capacity to invest in innovation, digitalisation, and sustainability.

From an industrial perspective, the new hub would have a significant impact on the entire Made in Italy supply chain, bringing together production districts, specialised subcontractors, and high-end artisans across central and northern Italy. This would strengthen skilled employment and promote the transfer of manufacturing expertise. From a financial standpoint, the merger would increase Italy’s appeal to institutional investors, reaffirming the country’s status as a luxury hub.

Ultimately, the operation combines both defensive and proactive strategies, aiming to reduce the dispersion of Italian brands under foreign conglomerates and promote the creation of a national cluster that can foster the continued evolution of Italian luxury heritage.

8.4 LIMITATIONS OF THE ANALYSIS

Although the methodology adopted aims to ensure a high level of consistency and robustness in the estimates, the analysis nonetheless presents several limitations that should be acknowledged.

First and foremost, it is necessary to reflect on the nature of the forecasting assumptions.

Since the revenue projections are based on the Revenue/GDP elasticity and on the geographical distribution of Versace's turnover, the model exhibits a certain degree of rigidity, as it does not account for potential shocks affecting either the brand or the sector as a whole. The main difficulty encountered was the inability to obtain coherent and high-quality data due to the legal status of Gianni Versace. Indeed, as Versace is a privately held company, financial statements are not always fully accessible for comprehensive analysis. As a result, it was necessary to rely on alternative sources, such as Capri Holdings' consolidated financial statements, sectoral reports, and benchmarks with listed competitors. This approach risks introducing distortions stemming from differences in scale, cost structures, margins, and market strategies.

It should also be noted that while the DCF remains the most accurate valuation model for estimating intrinsic value, it is nevertheless based on assumptions (such as WACC, cost of equity, and growth rate) that do not always converge with actual conditions. Even slight variations in these parameters may generate significant fluctuations in the estimated value. The DDM model was constructed to obtain a valuation for comparison with other methodologies, despite being based on the assumption that the company distributes dividends regularly. In contrast, historically neither Versace nor Capri Holdings has adopted such a policy.

At the same time, the multiples approach presents substantial limitations, as the peer group used for comparison is disproportionate in scale relative to Versace.

In light of the above, the DCF remains the only model that provides a sufficiently consistent estimate of intrinsic value, notwithstanding its strong dependence on the underlying assumptions. An additional limitation stems from the intangibility of brand value, a price component that is difficult to quantify using purely financial instruments. Although it is indirectly reflected in cash flows and market multiples, its measurement remains subject to considerable interpretation. In light of the foregoing, the results should be interpreted as a range of plausible valuation outcomes rather than as a precise, definitive point estimate of the value of Gianni Versace S.r.l.

8.5 LUXURY AS A POTENTIAL ASSET CLASS

In recent decades, the luxury sector has increasingly developed the characteristics of a distinct asset class, distinguishing itself from traditional industries and the broader consumer discretionary segment. It has become a form of alternative investment comparable to asset classes such as art, high-end real estate, or collectables, while retaining the liquidity typical of listed securities. This phenomenon stems from several unique features of the sector.

First and foremost, luxury exhibits a low correlation with traditional cyclical sectors, as

the leading listed luxury stocks have historically demonstrated a lower correlation coefficient compared with industrial and manufacturing indices, in some periods aligning more closely with sectors perceived as defensive. This has prompted growing interest in luxury as a diversification tool within portfolio construction.

A significant strength of the luxury sector lies in its ability to set prices above the market average, enabling brands to maintain their margins even in uncertain, inflationary, or recessionary contexts. This derives from the relative inelasticity of demand with respect to price, in contrast to typical consumer goods. In other words, luxury brands can pass a significant share of cost shocks on to consumers without experiencing substantial contractions in demand, thereby leveraging their pricing power.

On this basis, the luxury sector is increasingly viewed as capable of acting as a partial hedge against global uncertainty. From a capital markets perspective, this translates into improved investor sentiment and greater appeal to institutional investors who are increasingly seeking decorrelated and resilient investments. The growth in market capitalisation and enhanced liquidity further increases the group's attractiveness to large-cap funds, strengthening Prada's positioning within global thematic and sectoral indices.

In particular, the Prada–Versace transaction would enhance the group's critical mass, strengthening its bargaining power along the value chain. This would result in reduced margin volatility and a re-rating of market multiples, as investors tend to value positively the stability of future cash flows. It should also be noted that the integration of the two brands would improve Prada's capital risk profile by achieving greater geographical and product diversification, thereby reducing its equity beta.

At the same time, the merger would contribute to strengthening Prada's credit profile, leading to a compression of the cost of debt and, consequently, a reduction in the WACC, thereby increasing the DCF valuation. Furthermore, a sustainable financial structure would generate economies of scale and synergies, positively influencing rating agencies and resulting in tighter bond spreads and CDS premia. From a risk dynamics perspective, it can be assumed that idiosyncratic variance would decline owing to the offsetting of the specific risks of the two companies, thus producing more stable cash flows.

Beyond the points already outlined, it is worth noting that the luxury sector has demonstrated resilience in times of crisis in recent years. During the 2008 financial crisis, while sectors such as automotive and electronics experienced severe contractions, the leading luxury conglomerates were able to contain losses thanks to the growing weight of emerging markets and the loyalty of high-end clientele. Similarly, during the 2020 pandemic crisis, store closures and lockdowns led to a temporary decline in sales; however, the sector recovered through the adoption of technologies such as e-commerce and by leveraging its premium pricing power, regaining revenues more rapidly than other industries.

Another testing ground was the 2021 property crisis in China, which directly affected the sentiment of high-income Chinese consumers. Nevertheless, the major luxury groups succeeded in maintaining positive growth, thereby demonstrating resilience even in a context of localised stress in such a crucial market as China.

In this context, the combination of the two brands would contribute to creating a partial hedge against macroeconomic uncertainty by reducing dependence on individual markets and stabilising overall revenues.

In addition, their union would enhance the cultural relevance of the brands, sustained through collaborations with celebrities and visibility in music, cinema, and art, thereby reinforcing their resilience even during periods of economic downturn.

9 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Arrigo, E. (2018). Globalization strategies of luxury fashion brands: An exploratory study. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 9(2), 123–138. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20932685.2018.14>
- Bain & Company. (2024). *Luxury goods worldwide market study*.
- Beltrame, F., Mari, L., & Saita, F. (2021). *Corporate valuation*. Pearson.
- Bian, Q., & Forsythe, S. (2012). Purchase intention for luxury brands: A cross cultural comparison. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(10), 1443–1451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres>.
- Brun, A., & Castelli, C. (2013). The nature of luxury: A consumer perspective. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 41(11/12), 823–847. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-01-2013-0010>
- Camera Nazionale della Moda Italiana. (2023). *Fashion economic trends*.
- Capri Holdings. (2018). Press release: Acquisition of Versace.
- Caselli, S., & Gatti, S. (2019). *Analisi finanziaria e valutazioni d'azienda*. Egea.
- Cavender, R., & Rein, S. (2009). Luxury brand management: A world of privilege. *Journal of Brand Management*, 16(5–6), 338–346. <https://doi.org/10.1057/bm.2008.48>
- Chevalier, M., & Lu, P. (2012). *Luxury China: Market opportunities and potential*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Copeland, T., Koller, T., & Murrin, J. (2010). *Valuation: Measuring and managing the value of companies* (5th ed.). Wiley.

-
- Cucinelli, B. (2023). Relazione finanziaria annuale.
 - Damodaran, A. (2012). *Investment valuation: Tools and techniques for determining the value of any asset* (3rd ed.). Wiley.
 - Deloitte. (2023). Global powers of luxury goods.
 - Euromonitor International. (2024). Apparel and footwear in Western Europe and Asia-Pacific.
 - Gianni Versace S.r.l. (2023). Bilanci civilistici 2020–2024.
 - Hermès International. (2023). Universal registration document.
 - Kapferer, J. N., & Valette-Florence, P. (2016). Beyond rarity: The paths of luxury desire. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(1), 361–368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2015.07.002>
 - Ko, E., Costello, J. P., & Taylor, C. R. (2019). What is a luxury brand? A new definition and review of the literature. *Journal of Business Research*, 99, 405–413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.08.023>
 - Kering. (2023). Universal registration document.
 - KPMG
 - LVMH. (2023). Annual financial report.
 - McKinsey & Company. (2024). The state of fashion: Luxury outlook.
 - Morhart, F., Malär, L., Guevremont, A., Girardin, F., & Grohmann, B. (2015). Brand authenticity: An integrative framework. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 25(2), 200–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2014.11.006>
 - Okonkwo, U. (2007). *Luxury fashion branding: Trends, tactics, techniques*. Palgrave Macmillan.
 - Porter, M. E. (1985). *Competitive advantage: Creating and sustaining superior performance*. Free Press.
 - Prada S.p.A. (2023). Annual report 2023.
 - Richemont. (2023). Annual report 2023.
 - Statista. (2024). Luxury fashion market data and forecasts.

-
- Tynan, C., McKechnie, S., & Chhuon, C. (2010). Co-creating value for luxury brands. *Journal of Business Research*, 63(11), 1156–1163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2009.10.0>
 - Simone, S. , Marianna, D. , M. Firm Valuation in Practice: A DCF Application to Rheinmetall AG; <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=5337389>